

**FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE SEXUAL RISK BEHAVIOURS AMONG
ADOLESCENT BOYS IN SEROWE, BOTSWANA**

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DECLARATION

I declare that **FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE SEXUAL RISK BEHAVIOURS AMONG ADOLESCENT BOYS IN SEROWE, BOTSWANA** is my own original work, and that all the sources that I have used or quoted have been duly acknowledged and referenced as per university requirements, and that this work has not been submitted before for any other degree at any other institution before.

SIGNATURE

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25 June 2018

DATE

ABSTRACT

Background

Sexually active youths are at increased risk of contracting sexually transmitted infections including Human Immune Deficiency Virus (HIV). There are psychological and behavioural factors associated with sexual risk behaviours. Moreover, the prevalence of HIV in Botswana remains a public health concern that needs to be curbed from the level of young people in order to realize an HIV free generation. Therefore, the study aimed to explore factors that influence sexual risk behaviour among male adolescent.

Methods

A qualitative approach triangulating focus group discussions and in-depth interviews to explore factors that influence sexual risk behaviour among adolescent boys was carried out. Forty adolescent boys aged 13-20 years were purposively selected from the Serowe SOS Children's village residence in Botswana. Four focus group discussion and twelve one on one interviews were conducted. Data was analysed using thematic analysis described in Polit and Beck (2012:562).

Results

Four main themes emerged from the analysis of both individual interviews and focus group discussions as substance and alcohol use, peer pressure, lack of knowledge and domestic violence.

Conclusion

Health education on adolescent sexual reproductive health appears to have not made the desired outcome and needs to be reinforced. The study provides useful information that helps to understand why adolescent boys engage in risky sexual behaviours thus presenting an opportunity to improve adolescent sexual reproductive health programming for adolescent boys.

Keywords

Adolescence; Adolescents; Adolescent boys; Influence; Factors; Sexual risk behaviour

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Dedication

I dedicate this work to my two beautiful daughters and the strength that God provided throughout my learning.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ASRH	Adolescent Sexual Reproductive Health
BAIS	Botswana Aids Impact Survey
CDC	Centers for Disease Control
NACA	National Aids Coordinating Agency
STDs	Sexually transmitted diseases
STIs	Sexually Transmitted Infections
UNFPA	United Nations Fund for Population Activities
WHO	World Health Organization
UNISA	University of South Africa

CHAPTER 1

OVERVIEW OF THE STUDY

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a period of risk-taking and many adolescents choose to be sexually active and do so without protection (James & Ashwill 2007:202). The greatest concern to parents and guardians during adolescence are the adolescent's sexual experimentation and unwanted or unplanned pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections, including HIV. Fentahum and Mamo (2014:59-68) assert that youth engage in risky sexual behaviour for various reasons which include insufficient knowledge of reproductive health and family planning. These authors further add that the level of risks and sexual behaviours differ in males and females due to sexual exposure and socio economic factors. According to Kipping, Campbell, MacArthur, Gunnell and Hickman (2012:i1), the onset of multiple risk behaviours, such as smoking, anti-social behaviour, hazardous alcohol consumption and unprotected sexual intercourse cluster during adolescence. Therefore contextual understanding of risky sexual behaviours became an area of interest to the researcher so as to advance adolescent health promotion.

More than 30% of the world's population, that is over 1.7 billion people are aged 10-24, years representing a large group transitioning to adulthood. The United Nations estimates that by 2020, approximately 87% of the world's young population will be living in developing countries. By 2020, the global increase in population of 10-24 years olds in those countries is expected to be 33%. However, in Sub-Saharan Africa the corresponding increase is projected to be 25% (Department of Public Health 2011:1). In view of this upward trend in the global population of young people, it becomes crucial to promote adolescent health. The preventative approaches to sexually related illnesses remain important hence the intention of the present study to explore the factors that influence adolescent boys' sexual risk behaviour.

1.2 RESEARCH PROBLEM

The most critical stage of human development is arguably the adolescent stage, which is often characterised by a display of numerous delinquent behaviours. Of great concern is adolescents' involvement in forms of haphazard sexual activities which expose them to sexually transmitted infections (STIs) including HIV. These adolescents are sexually active, hormone driven individuals whose sexual activities have been viewed both negatively and as inappropriate (Edobor & Ekechukwu 2014:65).

The Department of Public Health (2011:12) states that out of a total of 1,567,000 of the Botswana population, 38% are the youth who are aged between the ages of 10-24 years. This figure reflects that Botswana has a large number of adolescents many of whom might already be sexually active.

Robinson (2010:1) states that "in 2005, approximately 48% of adolescents participating in the national Youth Risk Behaviour Survey reported being sexually active. Whilst being sexually active can be a normal aspect of adolescent development, the reported rates of unprotected sex and sex with multiple partners were alarmingly high. Of the students who reported being sexually active, 39% did not use condoms at their last intercourse". The Botswana Aids Impact Survey (BIAS III) estimated that 71% of young people aged 15-19 who had sex in the 12 months prior to the survey had it with a partner who was 10 or more years older. Close to a third (36%) of boys aged 20-24 had sex with more than one partner (BIAS III 2008:10).

Despite these risks, little research has been done in Botswana to explore factors influencing sexual risk behaviours. Most of the available studies (Ntshwarang & Malinga-Musamba, 2015; Letamo & Mokgathe 2013) done on risky sexual behavior in Botswana concentrated on girls and there are no studies that the researcher found on boys. Studies on risky sexual behaviours among adolescents do not mention boys as at risk group and even health care services, such as youth friendly services are designed with girls in mind. This identified gap prompted the researcher to look into factors that influence adolescent boys' engagement in sexual risky behaviours.

1.3 AIM OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study was to explore the factors that influence adolescent boys' sexual risk behaviour in Serowe, Botswana.

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

On the basis of the above, the objectives of the study were to

- explore factors that influence sexual risk behaviour among adolescent boys aged 13-20 years
- describe adolescent boys perceptions about sexual risk behaviours

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were posed:

- What factors influence adolescent boys sexual risk behaviours
- What are the perceptions of adolescent boys on sexual risk behaviours?

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

An investigation of sexual risk behaviours among adolescent boys in Botswana is important for the prevention of problems relating to sexually transmitted infections including HIV and AIDS. It is therefore imperative that this study will contribute to the development of sexual reproductive health programmes that specifically address the needs of adolescent boys. Such programmes will not only reduce the prevalence of sexual risk behaviours but also present an opportunity for youth to be engaged in programming that affects them. Moreover, the outcome of the study will have impact on sexual reproductive health programmes within the SOS Children's Village Organisation.

1.7 PERMISSION

Permission to undertake this study is necessary as compliance to the set national standards and the University of South Africa requirements. The permission is essential because it denotes that care must be exercised to ensure that participants' rights are protected. Therefore, the researcher obtained permission from two organisations before the study could be carried out.

1.7.1 Research Ethics Committee of the Department of Health Studies at UNISA

The proposal for this study was submitted to the research ethics committee of the Department of Health Studies at UNISA (Annexure A).

1.7.2 SOS Childrens's Villages Botswana

After permission was granted by the UNISA, permission was sought and granted by the SOS Childrens's Villages Botswana (Annexure B).

1.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The researcher followed three principles of the Belmont Report, namely beneficence, respect for human dignity as well as justice (Polit & Beck 2012:152).

1.8.1 Beneficence

According to Polit and Beck (2012:152), beneficence imposes a duty on researchers to minimise harm and maximise benefits and this principle involves the participant's right to freedom from harm and discomfort and the right to protection from exploitation. The researcher assured participants of their safety in the room where they were interviewed, she (researcher) encouraged the participants to be fearless and express their views and that whatever they shared would not be used against them in any way. The researcher

assured caregivers to the minors that their children will be provided with care and safety during the course of the study.

1.8.2 Respect for human dignity

Respect for human dignity includes the right to self-determination and right to full disclosure (Polit & Beck 2012:154). The researcher treated participants as autonomous entities by giving them the opportunity to make a voluntary decision to participate in the study. No adolescent was disregarded or coerced for non-participation. The researcher explicitly explained the purpose of the study and emphasized participants' protection and respect. This was done in the language understood by adolescents.

1.8.3 Justice

The third principle from Belmont Report concerns justice. Polit and Beck (2012:155) state that this principle includes participants' right to fair treatment and right to privacy. The researcher sensitively respected the participants' beliefs, habits, lifestyles, culture and emotions. The researcher further assured them of confidentiality, and the following precautions were adhered to:

- The list of names, transcriptions and notes were kept in a lockable cabinet.
- Names were not attached to the tapes or transcription or notes.

1.8.4 Informed consent

The notion of informed consent is an ethical research consideration that requires researchers to respect study participants' ability to decide their participation in the study. This empowers participants to make choices without being manipulated. It was therefore important for the researcher to share information on the purpose of the study to those involved. Participants were provided with explicit explanation on the aim of the study, how they were relevant to the study and the implication of the findings to practice and policy. The participants were offered freedom to decide whether to participate or not. Thereafter, they willingly completed the consent form and the minors' caregivers assented on their behalf.

1.9 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A qualitative descriptive research method was used in this study. Data were collected primarily through individual interviews, focus group discussions and observations during data collection. Four focus group discussions were held to validate the findings from the one-on-one interviews. Participants were recruited from the youth boy's programme at the SOS children's village in Serowe with their ages ranging between 13 and 20 years. A detailed discussion is provided in Chapter 3.

1.10 CONCEPTS DEFINITIONS

Adolescence: This refers to the period between onset of puberty and the cessation of physical growth; the passage from childhood to adulthood (James & Ashwil 2007:185). Kiragu, (1991:15) had defined adolescence as a transitional phase of development characterized by changes in physical characteristics from that of a child to that of an adult. The characteristics further include assumption of roles including those of reproductive and sexual health.

Adolescent: An individual aged 10-24 years as adopted and recognised by UNFPA, UNICEF and WHO (Department of Public Health 2011:8).

Adolescent boys: Males aged 10-24 years of age.

Adolescent sexuality: This refers to the thoughts, feelings and behaviours related to the adolescent's sexual identity.

Early adolescent: An adolescent aged 11-14 years accompanied by intense feeling about body image and many physical changes taking place (James & Ashwill 2007:192).

Factors: A wide range of measures relating to a particular subject (Sorensen & Hansen Report 2009:467).

Gender: This is the significance a society attaches to the biological categories of female and male. It is a socially constructed definition and refers to learned behaviour and experiences associated with each sex. (Department of Public Health 2011:9).

Influence: The capacity to have an effect on the character, development, or behaviour of someone or something (www.dictionary.com)

Late adolescence: The period around 18-21 years which is characterised by ability to think abstractly, conceptualise verbally, and express thoughts and feelings about various aspects of life (James & Ashwill 2007:194).

Middle adolescent: An individual aged 15-17 years who is often described by parents as most frustrating period where conformity to peer group norms became even more important, and conflicts between parents and adolescent/ teenagers escalate. (James & Ashwil 2007:193).

Perceptions: This refers to the meaning that people derive information received and processed through individual and social prisms (Rimal & Lapinski 2009:247).

Risk taking behaviour: Behaviours that predispose the adolescent to physical or psychological harm (James & Ashwill 2007:185).

Sexual development: This refers to the biological and psychosocial changes that lead to sexual maturity.

1.11. STRUCTURE OF THE DISSERTATION

The research study is structured in the following manner:

Chapter 1: Orientation of the study

This chapter presents an overview of the entire study. It highlights the background to the study through the description of risky sexual behaviours among adolescents with supportive statistics on why this study will add to the body of knowledge, the statement of the problem, research purpose and questions. This is followed by a presentation of the synopsis of the methodology and ethical principles followed in the study.

Chapter 2: Literature review

This chapter focuses on presenting some of the publications reviewed, as well the views of other researchers on the topic under study. The researcher reviewed available literature including “grey” literature, for deeper meaning and increased understanding of the research topic, along with methods that could be applied for study validity and precision. The literature review situates this study within previous studies done on the topic.

Chapter 3: Research Design and Method

This chapter will take the reader through the research design and methods employed during the study. The setting, population and sampling methods, as well the data collection and analysis plan of the study are described in detail. Issues of trustworthiness are also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter 4: Analysis, Presentation and Description of the Research Findings

In this Chapter, additional details on data management and analysis are presented. More importantly, the research findings are presented and the participants’ voices are used to enrich the findings.

Chapter 5: Discussion

This chapter presents further analysis and discussion of the findings presented in Chapter 4. The discussion links literature review with study findings.

Chapter 6: Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter contains conclusions prepared after the analysis of findings. The chapter discusses the limitations and implications of findings for nursing practice and provides recommendations for future practice and research.

1.12 CONCLUSION

In Chapter 1 the orientation of the study was given. The purpose and objectives of the study, and the research questions the study purports to answer, were discussed. The next chapter will discuss the literature review.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 1 gave the orientation and overview of the study. This chapter reviews the literature regarding the research topic “Factors that influence sexual risk behaviours among adolescent boys” by reviewing the sources discussed in section 2.3 of this chapter.

2.2 AIM OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature review aims at providing a summation of current findings and existing research evidence. The researcher considered a review of the existing sources on the research topic in order to inform the study. According to Polit and Beck (2012:95), carrying out literature review assists researchers to determine how best a researcher can contribute to the existing evidence for example, whether there are gaps or inconsistencies in a body of research, or whether a replication with new population is the right next step. Moreover, literature review also plays an important role when researchers try to make sense of their findings (Polit & Beck 2012:95). The information obtained from the literature review has therefore provided the foundation upon which the researcher based her reflections and conducted an investigation into the research problem.

For the purpose of this study, the review followed the conventional thinking by focusing on literary sources which explore the range of variables and factors considered causal to male adolescents' within the study area.

2.3 DATA SEARCH STRATEGY

Related studies (studies that met the eligibility criteria) to the topic under investigation were searched by browsing through several electronic databases and other resources and materials available at Serowe Institute of Health Sciences. The electronic databases included: PubMed Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health literature, Ebscohost and Proquest central. The search was limited to publications in English. The key search terms or phrases used in the search were:

- Adolescence
- Adolescent risky sexual behaviour globally and in Botswana
- Adolescent risky sexual behaviour among boys

Other sources of information included:

- WHO/UNAIDS manuals and reports
- References to books and e-books
- Subject-specific databases
- References to periodical articles in data-bases
- References to e-theses and dissertations

2.3.1 CRITERIA FOR INCLUSION OF RELATED LITERATURE WITHIN THE REVIEW

The eligibility criteria included the following:

- Types of participants: Studies whose participants were adolescents and in relation to sexual reproductive health were considered.
- Only studies which were published in English were included in the review.
- All reviewed studies were published pieces of research on adolescents' sexual behaviour.
- Both grey and recent literature on adolescent risky sexual behaviours were eligible for inclusion in the search

The literature reviewed has been broadened to enable the researcher and the readers a better understanding of the adolescence phase and the challenges faced that may

indirectly or directly influence adolescence 'risky sexual behaviours. The emphasis on the literature review is on male adolescents.

2.4 ADOLESCENCE AS A CONCEPT

The physical changes that indicate adolescence for boys include; the deepened voices, pubic hair and broadened shoulders. However, these physical changes represent just a fraction of the developmental processes that adolescent boys experience. Their developing brains bring new cognitive skills that enhance their ability to reason and to think abstractly. They develop emotionally, establishing a new sense of who they are and who they want to become. Their social development involves relating in new ways both to peers and adults. And, they begin to experiment with new behaviours as they transition from childhood to adulthood (American Psychological Association 2002:5).

Although often captured as an age range, chronological age is just one way of defining adolescence. Adolescence can also be defined in numerous other ways, considering such factors as physical, social, cognitive development, as well as age. For example, another definition of adolescence might be the period of time from the onset of puberty until an individual achieves economic independence (American Psychological Association 2002:2). Botswana's Ministry of Health (2003:7) defines adolescence as a stage marked by maturation of physical and psychological aspects. In this period the individual boy is no longer a child, but not yet an adult. This developmental period is fraught with promises and pitfalls thereby making the transition uneven with physical maturity preceding psychological; and social maturity.

Idele, Gillespie, Porth, Suzuki, Mahy, Kasedde and Luo (2014:S144) describe adolescence as a period when many people begin to explore their sexuality. As a result, access to sexual and reproductive health information and services become very important. Moreover, Steinberg 2014 in Curtis (2015:1) define adolescence as a dynamically evolving theoretical construct informed through physiologic, psychosocial, temporal and cultural lenses and that this period is understood as the years between the onset of puberty and the establishment of social independence. In this context, adolescence is a developmental stage that each individual go through with varying phases of how he resolves the stage. In addition the World Health Organization (WHO) (2014) defines adolescence as a period of life with specific health and developmental needs and rights. It is a time to develop knowledge and skills, learn to manage emotions and relationships, and acquire attributes and abilities that will be important for

enjoying adolescent years and assuming adult roles. Furthermore, the WHO (2014:1) further define adolescents as people aged between 10 to 19 years of age and that it may be defines differently from one country to the other depending on their contextual definitions.

The process of adolescence involves preparation for adulthood, and during that time several key developmental experiences occur. Besides physical and sexual maturation, these experiences include movement toward social and economic independence, and development of identity, the acquisition of skills needed to carry out adult relationships and roles, and the capacity for abstract reasoning. While adolescence is a time of tremendous growth and potential, it is also a time of considerable risk during which social contexts exert powerful influences (WHO 2016:2).

In view of the above definitions, adolescents are diverse in nature which means that there is need for a better understanding and deeper assessment of adolescents as well as their varying and unique needs. The next section discusses the developmental stages of adolescence.

2.4.1 Stages of adolescence development

Adolescence is a time of great change for young people. It is a time when physical changes are happening at an accelerated rate. But adolescence is not just marked by physical changes; young people are also experiencing cognitive, social, emotional and interpersonal changes as well. As they grow, adolescents are influenced by outside factors such as parents, peers, community, culture, religion and school, world events and media. There are a number of theories that guide an understanding of adolescent development. These theories have a unique focus and have similar elements as stipulated below (Spano 2004:1).

Table 2:1 THEORIES OF ADOLESCENT DEVELOPMENT

An understanding of the concept of adolescence as a developmental stage characterised and interpreted from different theoretical perspectives is important to this study hence the following discussion.

Developmental area	Primary theorist	Main focus
BIOLOGICAL	G Stanley Hall Arnold Gesell James Tanner	Focuses on adolescence as a period of physical and sexual development determined by genes and biology.
PSYCHOLOGICAL	Stigmund Freud Anna Freud	Focuses on adolescence as a period sexual excitement and anxiety
PSYCHOSOCIAL	Erick Erickson	The focus of the stage is on identity formation; adolescents struggle between achieving identity and identity diffusion
COGNITIVE	Jean Peaget	The focus is on formal operational thought; moving beyond concrete, actual experiences and beginning to think in logical and abstract terms
ECOLOGICAL	Urie Bronfenbrenner	Focus is on the context in which adolescents develop; adolescents are influenced by family, peers, religion, schools, media, community and world events.
SOCIAL COGNITIVE LEARNING	Albert Bandura	Focus is on the relationship between social and environmental factors and their influence on behaviour
CULTURAL	Margaret Mead Carol Gilligan	Focus is on the culture within which a child grows.

The chronological stages of adolescence, according to Spano (2004 1-3) embrace the following:

1. Early adolescent (approximately 10-14 years of age)
2. Middle adolescence (approximately 15-16 years of age)
3. Late adolescence (approximately 17-21 years of age)

These stages are described in the next sections with respect to the following aspects:

- I. Movement toward independence
- II. Future interest and cognitive development,
- III. Sexuality
- IV. Physical changes
- V. Ethics and self-directions

2.4.1.1 Early adolescence (approximately 10-14 years of age)

This stage is discussed in broad areas as follows:

Movement toward independence: This stage is characterised by emerging identity shaped over time by internal and external influences; moodiness; improved abilities to use speech to express oneself; more likely to express feelings by action than by words (may be more true for males); close friendships gain importance; less attention shown to parents, with occasional rudeness; realisation that parents are not perfect; identification of their own faults; search for new people to love in addition to parents; tendency to return to childish behavior

ur during times of stress; peer group influence on personal interests and clothing styles.

Future interests and cognitive development: This stage is characterised by increasing career interests; mostly interested in present and near future; greater ability to work.

Sexuality: Boys tend to be curious with their bodies.

Physical changes: This stage is characterised by gains in height and weight; growth of pubic and underarm hair; increased perspiration - body odour develops; increased oil production of hair, growth of testicles and penis, nocturnal emissions (wet dreams), deepening of voice, growth of hair on face in boys.

Ethics and self-direction: This stage is characterised by rule and limit testing; occasional experimentation with cigarettes, marijuana, and alcohol; capacity for abstract thought (Spano 2004:1-3).

2.4.2.2 Middle adolescence (approximately 15-16 years of age)

According to Spano (2004:2) this stage is characterised as follows:

Movement toward Independence: This stage is characterised by self-involvement, alternating between unrealistically high expectations and worries about failure; complaints that parents interfere with independence; extremely concerned with appearance and with one's own body; feelings of strangeness about one's self and body; lowered opinion of and withdrawal from parents; effort to make new friends; strong emphasis on the new peer group; periods of sadness as the psychological loss of parents takes place; examination of inner experiences, which may include writing a diary.

Future interests and cognitive development: This stage is characterised by intellectual interests gain importance; some sexual and aggressive energies directed into creative and career interests; anxiety can emerge related to school and academic performance (Spano 2004:2).

Sexuality: Spano (2004:2) further states that this stage is characterised by concerns about sexual attractiveness; frequently changing relationships; more clearly defined sexual orientation, with internal conflict often experienced by those who are not heterosexual; tenderness and fears shown toward opposite sex; feelings of love and passion .

Physical changes: This stage is characterised by males showing continued height and weight gains. Masculine body changes become noticeable.

Ethics and self-direction: This stage is characterised by development of ideals and selection of role models; more consistent evidence of conscience; greater goal setting capacity; interest in moral reasoning.

2.4.3.3 Late adolescence (approximately 17-21 years of age)

This stage is discussed as follows according to Spano (2004:3-4).

Movement toward independence: This stage is characterised by firmer identity; ability to delay gratification; ability to think through ideas; ability to express ideas in words; more developed sense of humour; interests become more stable; greater emotional stability; ability to make independent decisions; ability to compromise; pride in one's work; self-reliance; greater concern for others.

Future interests and cognitive development: This stage is characterised by more defined work habits; higher level of concern for the future; thoughts about one's role in life.

Sexuality: This stage is characterised by concerned with serious relationships; clear sexual identity; capacities for tender and sensual love.

Physical changes: This stage is characterised by young men who continue to gain height, weight, muscle mass, body hair. Ethics and Self-Direction: capable of useful insight; focus on personal dignity and self-esteem; ability to set goals and follow through; acceptance of social institutions and cultural traditions; self-regulation of self-esteem.

2.5. ADOLESCENTS SEXUAL RISK BEHAVIOUR GLOBALLY

According to Hall, Holmqvist and Sherry (2004:4), risky sexual behaviours can take many forms ranging from multi sexual partners, unprotected vaginal, oral or anal intercourse and engaging in sexual intercourse under the influence of alcohol or substance. Fenrahun and Mamo (2014:59) argue that youth engage in sexual risk behaviour due to insufficient knowledge of reproductive health and that the risks are different between male and female due to sexual exposure and socio cultural factors. Adolescents are therefore likely to engage in risky sexual practices such as engaging in

multiple partner relationships, experimenting unprotected sex and increase sexual activities.

The timing of first sexual intercourse and the context in which it occurs both have health implications. In some parts of the world, for instance in North Africa and parts of Asia, most sexual activity reported even 10-15 years ago takes place within the context of marriage. A study with data from 14 countries showed that the context of early sexual experience often differs between young men and young women, especially in developing regions. For boys, most sexual relationships during the teenage years are non-marital. In girls, a sizeable proportion notably the largest proportion in some developing countries occurs within marriage. In most countries of the developed world and sub-Saharan Africa (except Nigeria and Rwanda), a third or more of unmarried adolescent girls have had sexual intercourse. In the Philippines, Eastern Europe, and Latin America, smaller proportions of girls have had intercourse, ranging from less than 1% in Azerbaijan and the Republic of Georgia to 30% in the Ukraine. In most countries, more than 40% of unmarried adolescent boys have had intercourse, compared with less than a third in Nigeria, Rwanda, and the Philippines. Young people who have several sexual partners are at increased risk of contracting STIs, including HIV. In countries where data are available, a substantially larger proportion of adolescent boys than girls have had two or more partners in the past year. These differences might in part be due to cultural pressures on boys to prove their virility. The double standard for sexual behaviour, whereby restraint is expected of girls and excesses are tolerated for boys, compounds reproductive health problems for both sexes (Bearinger et al 2007:1221).

In the United States, according to the 2009 Youth Risk Behaviour Survey, students in Grades 9 through 12 were less likely to report sexual intercourse with at least one person compared with students surveyed in 2003. The survey indicated that 46% of students had sexual intercourse with at least one person, and 5.9% of students had sexual intercourse for the first time before age 13 years. The National Survey for Family Growth was conducted by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's (CDC) National Center for Health Statistics. Over the year before the survey, 13% of 15 to 17-year-old males and 11% of 15 to 17-year-old females had heterosexual oral sex but not vaginal intercourse. Fourteen percent of students reported sexual intercourse with four or more persons during the stage under review Sixty-one percent of students reported

that either they or their partner had used a condom during their last sexual encounter. The prevalence of having used a condom during last sexual intercourse was higher among male (69%) than female (54%) students (Tulloch & Kaufman 2013:31).

The median age of first intercourse for male and female subjects in Canada is 16.5 years according to a Canadian study that included 1,171 participants age 14 to 17 years across the country (11). The mean age of first oral sex in this study was 15 years. Five percent of boys and 1% of girls initiated intercourse before age 12 years. Approximately 30% of boys and 20% of girls had experienced sexual intercourse at least once by age 14 years. Among the teens who become sexually active, 68% reported oral sex and 85% reported vaginal intercourse. Seventy-six percent reported condom use the last time they had intercourse. Nine percent reported the use of the withdrawal method, and 1% used emergency contraception. In 2008, the British Columbia Adolescent Health Survey (a cluster-stratified weighted survey) obtained data from more than 280,000 students from grades 7 through 12. Twenty-six percent of students reported ever having oral sex, and the percentages were similar for male and female students. The percentages increased from 3% among students 12 years or younger to 52% of students 18 years or older. The trend with condom use declined with age, and oral contraceptive pill use increased with age. Among the students who reported sexual activity, 32% reported that they drank alcohol or used drugs before their last sexual encounter (Tulloch & Kaufman 2013:31).

In 2006, 61% of 15-year-old sexually active females in the Netherlands reported using the birth control pill at their last sexual encounter. In the United States among sexually active females in grades 9 through 12, 10% reported using dual methods (eg, condoms with birth control pills or medroxyprogesterone injection). Among sexually active male students, 8% used dual methods in which they used a condom and their partner used birth control pills or medroxyprogesterone (Tulloch & Kaufman 2013:31).

Chanakira, O’Cathain, Goyder and Freeman (2014:1055) state that in the United Kingdom (UK) high rates of the most commonly diagnosed sexually transmitted infections (STIs) tend to be observed among young people under 25-years-old. For instance, the UK prevalence rates for chlamydia are highest among 18-19 year old women (4.7%) and men aged 20-24 years (3.4%) and for human papillomavirus (high-

risk types) women aged 18-19 years have the highest rates (29.6%) followed by those in the 20-24 year age group (26.6%). These high rates of infection are mainly due to risky sexual lifestyles (such as having intercourse without a condom, having multiple sexual partners and having one night stands referred to as casual sex of these age groups (Chanakira et al 2014:1055).

In a study to examine the influence of adolescent high-risk sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis by Edobor and Ekechukwu (2014:62) the results revealed that adolescents are involved in high-risk sexual behaviour and that male adolescents (boys) are highly prone to risky sexual act than the female folk (girls) due to their high psycho-sexual urge “libido”.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, which includes almost two-thirds of all youth living with HIV worldwide, the main mode of transmission is heterosexual intercourse. Tremendous diversity exists across the subcontinent in rates of HIV infection, with Southern Africa being the worst affected region in the world. About 75% of all young people living with HIV in sub-Saharan Africa are female. Prevalence is higher in adolescent girls than in adolescent boys in all countries, with the ratio of girls to boys living with HIV ranging from 20 to ten in South Africa, to 45 to ten in Kenya and Mali (Bearinger et al 2007:1224). The global male adolescent indulgence in risky sexual behaviours remains important to this study for the purposes of finding out possible programmatic solutions to boys’ sexual reproductive health.

2.6 ADOLESCENT SEXUAL RISK BEHAVIOUR IN BOTSWANA

Botswana is one of the countries hardest hit by HIV in the world. By 2008 HIV prevalence was estimated at 17.61% in the population. HIV prevalence among boys and girls is almost the same for up to 14 years of age. However, among the age groups 15-19 and 20-24 years girls are twice likely to be infected as boys (National Aids Coordinating Agency, Wise Up Campaign 2014:1). The 2008 Botswana AIDS Impact survey shows that about 18 000 children aged 10-19 are HIV positive (Statistics Botswana 2008). Many of these adolescents are undiagnosed and therefore do not know their status. The HIV epidemic is already generalised among adolescents and

young people. Even though the prevalence decreased between 2004 and 2008 in these age groups, the HIV prevalence among the age groups 20-24 years is three times as high as that of the age group 15-19 years (National Aids Coordinating Agency, Wise Up Campaign 2014:2). This shows that young people do not have the required information and skills to safely transit from one stage of life to the next. By age 17 years, half of the boys in Botswana have had sex. As in many countries in southern Africa young people engage in risky sexual behaviours and do not always consider themselves to be at risk of HIV infection.

Thupayagale-Tshweneagae, Seboni and Seloilwe (2009:3) have observed that HIV and AIDS are a major problem in Botswana and have affected young people, most of whom have been infected with HIV during their teenage years. They further add that prevalence among young people aged 15-24 is 16.9% and 6.6% among adolescents aged 15-19 years. The BIAS III estimated that 7% of young people aged 15-19 years who had sex in the 12 months before the survey had it with a partner who was 10 or more years older. Close to one third(36%) of the boys aged 20-24 had sex with more than one partners in the 12months before the BIAS III, compared to about one tenth (16%) for girls in the same ages group (National Aids Coordinating Agency Wise up Campaign 2014:1-2).

The Botswana Youth Risk Behavioural Surveillance Survey of 2013 among 10-19 years old students revealed the following facts concerning adolescents (The Botswana Youth Risk Behavioural Surveillance Survey 2013)

Sexual behaviour

The survey revealed that:

- 20.5% of students had ever had sexual intercourse.
- 8.1% of students had sexual intercourse in the past 12 months prior to the survey.
- Of those 20.5% sexually experienced students:
 - o 19.1% had sexual intercourse for the first time before age 13 years.
 - o 55% used a condom the first time they had sexual intercourse.

- o 39.3% had sexual intercourse in the past 12 months.
- o 19.3% had sexual intercourse with two or more people in the past 12 months.
- o 9.4% of girls reported having been pregnant and 8.9% of boys reported having impregnated someone.

Substance use, physical and sexual violence

The Botswana Youth Risk Behavioural Surveillance Survey (2013) further show that:

- 13.8% of students had ever used snuff.
- 18.6% of students had ever smoked a cigarette and 7.1% of students had smoked a cigarette on at least one day during the 30 days prior to the survey (current cigarette use).
- 16.6% of students had ever had at least one drink of alcohol and 7.3% of students reported having had at least one drink of alcohol in the past 30 days (current alcohol use).
- 14.9% of students reported having ever used marijuana, 5.6% had ever used cocaine, 3.7% had ever used ecstasy, and 5.7% had ever used sextasy.
- 40% of students reported having been picked on or bullied during the 30 days prior to the survey.
- 25.1% of students were threatened or injured with a weapon during the 30 days prior to the survey.
- 28.2% of students were involved in a physical fight and had to be treated by a doctor or nurse during the 12 months prior to the survey.
- 13% of sexually experienced students had been raped the first time they had sexual intercourse.
- 12.8% of sexually experienced students were forced to have sexual intercourse during the 12 months prior to the survey.

The survey reflects the escalating risky sexual behaviour becoming more common amongst adolescents in Botswana. However, the existing literature show little on the adolescent boys hence the intention of the study to carryout an exploration of factors that influence risk sexual behaviours among the adolescent boys.

Melles (2009:1) shares the following facts concerning youth or adolescents reproductive and sexual health:

Young people aged 10 to 24 comprise 700,000, or 38.9% of the 1.8 million people living in Botswana. This group of young people is the largest group ever to be entering adulthood in Botswana's history. But largely because of the devastation caused by HIV and AIDS, young people in Botswana, especially young women, face many challenges to their sexual and reproductive health, including high rates of maternal mortality, increased risk of violence and HIV due to widespread alcohol abuse, and the second highest HIV prevalence of any nation. In one study, among young people ages 15-24, 88% of men and 75% of women used a condom at their last high-risk sexual activity (Melles 2009:1).

Moreover, Melles (2009:1) asserts that there is no formal sex education in schools in Botswana, and that many parents are uncomfortable talking about sexuality with their children. However, young people receive some information about sexuality and HIV prevention both informally from friends and acquaintances, and through Botswana's HIV prevention social marketing programs (Melles 2009:1).

The decision to become sexually active with resulting adolescent pregnancy whether planned or not, is directly influenced by the teenager's beliefs. In further expounding this assertion the following study is presented to further guide an apprehension of contributing factors to adolescents sexual risk behaviours.

In their study on Oral communication: a gateway to understanding adolescents' sexual risk behaviour, Ntshwarang and Malinga-Musamba (2015:106-109) reported the following:

The study revealed some sexual behaviours (condom use and multiple partners) that adolescents' boys engage in. It also revealed that adolescents receive mixed messages about sexual behaviours. The messages from proverbs, metaphorical sayings, songs and stories communicated by their peers have a potential to encourage sexually risky behaviours although parents discourage such sexual behaviours. Adolescents have

created a culture of their own in which they want to be accepted by their peers and have a feeling of belonging. Even though that is the case, they still feel that they are being pressured by their peers to have sex. Stories have also been coined around the issue of abstinence, for example students reported that some students in school, especially boys, tell them that if adolescents stay virgins for a long time, by the time they have sexual intercourse, the sex organs will be painful which will lead to a very good orgasm resulting in death. This story discourages others from abstaining (Ntshwarang & Malinga-Musamba 2015:106).

2.7 ADOLESCENT RISKY SEXUAL BEHAVIOUR AMONG BOYS

Kipping, Campbell, MacArthur, Gunnell & Hickman (2012:i1) highlight that interaction and occurrence of multi and sexual risk behaviours occur more in adolescence than in adults. However, Kipping et al (2012:i1) further assert that these behaviours (anti-social behaviour, smoking, hazardous alcohol consumption and unprotected sexual activities) shape adulthood behaviour and the consequences are costly to society and young people.

Furthermore Idele et al's (2014:S144) report that adolescence is typically a period of experimentation. In this phase adolescents begin to experience coital relationships and are vulnerable to risks such as use of drugs, and may experiment with other males for fun and unprotected sex is common among this age group. Nzioka (2001:108) shares that despite a high knowledge of sexual risks fear of HIV and awareness of the protective value of condoms, the young men exhibit high risk behaviour. They feel the need to conform to the common social prescriptions of early sexual experience and having more than one partner.

Fenrahun and Mamo (2014:59) argue that youth engage in sexual risk behaviour due to insufficient knowledge of reproductive health and that the risks are different between male and female due to sexual exposure and socio cultural factors. Adolescents are therefore likely to engage in risky sexual practices such as engaging in multiple partner relationships, experimenting unprotected sex and increase sexual activities.

A recent study examined incidence from 1985 to 1996 of three common STIs; gonorrhoea, syphilis, and chlamydia using national statistics for 15-19-year-olds from 16

developed countries. The incidence of these three diseases decreased between the mid-1980s and the mid-1990s, in the general population and in adolescents. For all STIs studied, incidence was generally higher for adolescent girls than for boys, partly because girls were more likely to be screened. In the mid-1990s, the incidence of gonorrhoea in adolescents was fairly low less than ten per 100,000 in nine countries, and ten to 20 in one country studied. Incidence of gonorrhoea was distinctly higher in the Russian Federation and the USA, where rates approached 600 per 100,000. Incidence of syphilis in adolescents was also low, with most countries reporting rates of less than three cases per 100,000. Worldwide, 6 000 young people are estimated to be infected with HIV every day. (Bearinger et al 2007:1224)

2.7.1 Factors influencing sexual risk behaviour

Sexual behaviour is complex and influenced by a wide array of personal, social, cultural, moral and environmental factors. According to Karim & Karim (2010:161), sexual risk behaviour is shaped or influenced by three levels of factors that reciprocally influence each other. These are personal factors, factors in proximal context and distal context. Their framework of understanding risk sexual behaviour presents these factors as follows.

2.7.1.1 Personal factors

These are factors that reside within the individual such as cognition and feelings towards sexual behaviour and HIV/AIDS and thoughts about oneself. In the review by Kalichman et al (2010:420) on the South African youth, self-efficacy for condom use is associated with higher self-reported use. It also showed that low self-esteem is associated with earlier sex debut, having more sexual partners and having negative attitude towards condom use.

2.7.1.2 Proximal factors

This context encompasses features of relationships and environment that affect an individual. These are related to interpersonal relations, sexual relationships, peer

pressure, family relations and health services. Families provide the most proximal and fundamental social system for influencing positive family relations, communication about sexuality and safer sex behaviours as well as monitoring peer activities (Karim & Karim 2010:161). Furthermore, Kirby and Lepore (2007:6) describe those environmental factors those that characterise the community in which a teen lives, his or her family, peers and best friends, and the teen's romantic partners. Rwenge (2000:118) outlines that a wide range of studies carried across the world indicate that strict parental monitoring is positively associated with reduced adolescent health risk, delayed intercourse, fewer sexual partners and consistent contraceptive use (Dekeke & Sandy 2014:20). This indicates that family as a social factor plays an important role in the adolescents' sexual behaviour. If sex education and guidance is not provided by family or caregivers, it becomes inevitable that youngsters will indulge in unsafe sexual practices.

Family circumstances are very important in determining risk. Teens or adolescents who live with both parents and enjoy close relationships with them are less likely to have unprotected sex and become pregnant. Specifically, if teens live with both biological parents (instead of only one parent or step-parents), they are less likely to have sex, but if they do, they are likely to have sex less frequently. According to Kirby and Lepore (2007:6-7) a majority of studies finds that teens living with both parents are less likely to become pregnant (or cause a pregnancy) or to give birth (or father a child). If biological parents divorce or separate, their children are more likely to initiate sex at an early age than if the parents do not divorce or separate. Teens whose parents have a sound education are less likely to become pregnant than teens whose parents have less education. Family income is also a factor: the majority of studies found that teens in families with higher incomes were less likely to become pregnant or to bear children (Kirby & Lepore 2007:6-7).

Abuse of alcohol or drugs in the family increases the chances that teens will have sex more frequently and with more partners (Kirby & Lepore 2007:6-7). They assert two possible reasons for this effect: family substance abuse may encourage young people to drink and use drugs themselves, which can lead to more frequent sex with more partners, or family substance abuse may simply be a marker for more general family dysfunction, which can lead to sexual risk taking by teens. If family members, especially

parents, express values or model behaviour consistent with sexual risk-taking or early childbearing, teens are more likely to have unprotected sex and become pregnant (or cause their partners to become pregnant). Parents may do this in a variety of ways, including conveying permissive attitudes about premarital sex or teen sex, voicing negative attitudes about contraception, or having been teen parents themselves. Similarly, teens whose older siblings model early sex or childbearing are more likely to have early sex themselves. In contrast, parental disapproval of teen sex reduces the chances that teens will have sex, and parental support of contraceptive use increases the chances that teens will use contraception if they do have sex. When parents have conversations with their children about sex and contraception well before the children become sexually active, the initiation of sex may be delayed and the use of condoms or other contraceptives increased. This effect is most likely to occur when the teen is a daughter (as opposed to a son), when the parent is the mother (as opposed to the father), when the teens and their parents feel connected to one another, when the parents disapprove of teens having sex or support contraceptive use, and when parents can discuss sexuality in an open and comfortable manner (Kirby & Lepore 2007:6-7).

Peer pressure has been identified as a mediating factor of high risk sexual behaviour among young people. This assertion is supported variously by scholars as cited in Dekeke and Sandy (2014:22) as follows:

Kirby and Lepore (2007:123) state that “peer pressure encourages youth to experiment a range of sexual behaviours and doing so may lead to increased risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases including HIV/AIDS”.

Thupayagale-Tshweneagae (2010:56) observes that “the influence of peer pressure on such risk behaviour is probably because youths have the potential to internalise the opinions of their peers and externalise the same in the presence of the sexual partners”.

Kirby and Lepore (2007:7) report that teens are more likely to have sex if their best friends and peers are older, use alcohol or drugs, or engage in other negative behaviour. Similarly, they are more likely to have sex if they believe their friends have more positive attitudes toward childbearing, have permissive values about sex, or are actually having sex. If teens believe their friends support condom use or actually use

condoms, chances are greater that they will use condoms themselves. This discussion shows that at an interpersonal level, peer pressure influences behaviour development and learning. Therefore it is fundamental that adolescent behaviour development or learning be guided through to address pressure from peers. The quality and existence of sexual reproductive health services and programmes adds to the behaviour outcomes displayed by adolescents. This further indicates that without proper and adequate sexual reproductive health services, adolescents remain vulnerable to risky behaviours.

2.7.1.3 Distal context

This encompasses cultural and religious factors pertaining to sexual behaviour. Religion has been cited to be critical in shaping the beliefs and choices that people generally make. This is evident from a study by Kristin and Richard (2009:163) arguing that youth who perceived or viewed religion as an important aspect in their lives were likely to have fewer sexual partners and those with strong religious affiliations were less likely to indulge in sexual activity before marriage. From a Christian perspective, this concept encourages abstinence and in cases where an adolescent is firmly a believer, he or she delays sexual practices as way of obedience to God.

In addition, culture as the way of life is critical to the influence of sexual behaviour. Cultural settings that promote unsafe or unprotected sexual intercourse and multi partner sexual relations present a challenge to the display of sexual risk of behaviours. These cultures are those that promote polygamy and the non-involvement of a woman in the subject of sexual intercourse. The intake of alcohol or substance use is a culture that characterises some population groups and societal segments such as adolescents/youth, males and middle to high level tertiary institution inhabitants. The WHO (2014) reports that sexual risk behaviour accounts for a large number of opportunities for acquiring HIV infection, and alcohol use has been shown to increase high-risk sexual behaviour. Moreover, the social dynamics that surround alcohol use, sexual risk behaviour and HIV infection necessitates the need for an intervention that incorporates social and cultural issues relating to sexual behaviour.

The literature also identifies four factors that have been associated with risky sexual behaviours and pregnancy: race and ethnicity; socioeconomic status; social influences; and attitudes toward contraception, condoms and pregnancy and safer-sex behavioural skills (Kalmuss et al 2003:87-93).

A teenager's own level of academic achievement is positively related to age at sexual debut. Young people's social influences clearly affect their likelihood of engaging in risky behaviours, particularly early sexual debut and non-use of condoms. For example, having friends who are sexually active or who do not use condoms enhances one's own risk of these behaviours. In addition Dekeke and Sandy (2014:21) share that the Ethiopian Behavioural Surveillance Survey of 2005 indicates that males are more likely to have multiple partners and experience early sexual initiation than females thus they are at a higher risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases.

The available literature review presented in this chapter provides a wide range of information on the adolescents girls as compared to the adolescent boys sexual risk behaviours. Therefore, it is from this premise that the study focused on exploring the factors that influence the risky sexual behaviours on adolescent boys.

2.8 Strategies to improve sexual risk behaviour

In many communities, programs to reduce young people's risk of contracting HIV infection, sexually transmitted diseases (STDs), and pregnancy are fragmented, intermittent, short-term, and problem-focused. Young people may receive some HIV education in some grades in school, but many students receive little or no contraceptive education, and many young people such as youth who are not in school receive almost no HIV/STD or contraceptive education (Pagliaro & Klindera 2001:1). A number of relational factors are also relevant to facilitating behaviour change in adolescents. One such set of variables includes the need for self-determination, and perceptions of autonomy (Hall et al 2004:4). They further allude that self-determination theory suggests that individuals are more motivated to make and sustain behaviour change when they perceive that they are doing it for internal (e.g, personally held values) rather than for external reasons (e.g, pressure from family, friends, caregivers). From these recollections, it may become apparent that those who truly value changes internally are

more likely to overcome inevitable obstacles to behaviour change than those patients who are "doing it because someone wants me to." This approach of appealing to the adolescent's own reasons could be termed "autonomy supportive" based on the premise that there is recognition of the adolescent's need for self-determination. A key intervention strategy when dealing with adolescents, then, is to maximise autonomy support (Hall et al 2004:4).

It is explicit that behaviour modification is central to internal processes of self-determination, efficacy and decision making. These are central to dealing with external factors such as peer pressure, poor parental control and guidance as well as inadequate access to sexual reproductive health education and programmes. Dekeke and Sandy (2014:20) assert that communication between parents and their children about sexual issues is persistently reported to play a role in preventing young people from sexual risk behaviours.

Moreover programmatic strategies should begin earlier and target younger adolescents. Since adolescents who experience early puberty are at increased risk for early sexual activity, primary health care providers should be screening and counselling youth regarding puberty, sex and sexual risk behaviours at younger ages than they currently do. Adolescents should then be provided with developmentally appropriate educational and counselling messages that are responsive to the young person's stage of sexual activity (Kalmuss et al 2003:88).

Furthermore, Terzian, Andrews and Moore (2011:1) state that preventing multiple risky behaviours among adolescents should involve cost effective and rigorous strategies that embrace the following:

- a) Support and strengthen family functioning.
- b) Increase connections between students and their schools.
- c) Make communities safe and supportive for children and youth.
- d) Promote involvement in high quality out-of-school-time programs.
- e) Promote the development of sustained relationships with caring adults.
- f) Provide children and youth opportunities to build social and emotional competence.

- g) Provide children and youth with high quality education during early and middle childhood.

Adolescents lack real-life experiences and interpersonal skills needed to implement many HIV risk reduction actions, such as negotiating for safer sex. Furthermore, several developmental transitions affect the onset of sexual activity, and subsequent risk behaviours. Therefore it is important to develop appropriate interventions that address the varying patterns of adolescent sexual behaviour.

2.6 CONCLUSION

There is general consensus that the proportion of teenagers who engage in behaviours that put them at risk remains too high. One factor motivating early intercourse may be that male peer group norms endorse early sex as a way to prove masculinity and thus solidify social standing. Knowing the motivation behind and nature of early sexual experiences among young men is critical for designing counselling and educational programs that are grounded in the reality of their lives. Literature revealed the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among adolescents with more evidence on factors that influence the girl child's involvement into sexual practices as compared to an adolescent boy. Increased unsafe sexual activity is risky to both male and female adolescents.

Preventing infection in adolescents and youth as well as supporting those who are living with HIV starts with understanding the attitudes and behaviours of young people is crucial. One indicator that measures high-risk behaviour is the proportion of sexually active young people that have had multiple sexual partners and when young people engage in unprotected sex with many different partners. They increase their chances of becoming infected with HIV.

The status report on adolescents and young people in Sub-Saharan Africa by United Nations Population Fund (2012:18-19) says that according to data from Sub-Saharan Africa, male youth are more likely to report having multiple partners in the last year than female youth. In fact, nearly half of the countries with available data are considered "red", meaning more than one of every five sexually active young men reported having

multiple partners. It is therefore imperative that this study investigates the adolescent boy's risk sexual behaviour in order to gain a contextual understanding that will consequently inform strategies and programmes to promote the boys sexual reproductive health.

Literature has substantially defined the concept of sexual risk behaviour, adolescent risk sexual behavior in Botswana and globally, factors associated with boys sexual risk behaviours, and strategies that may be employed in addressing existing gaps in the adolescent boys' reproductive health. Therefore, the following chapters discuss the findings and analysis of the study carried out in SOS Children's home in Serowe, Botswana.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides a comprehensive description of the research design and methodology that the researcher used in this study. The research design, methods, data collection, data analysis, trustworthiness and ethical considerations relevant to the study are discussed in this chapter. The researcher explored factors that influence risk sexual behaviours among adolescent boys using a qualitative approach.

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

A research design is a plan for conducting a study. It is the entire process of research (conceptualizing a problem, writing research questions, collecting data, analysis, interpretation and report writing) (Creswell 2013:5, 49). It involves a set of decisions regarding what topic to be studied, among what population, with what research methods and for what purpose. It is the overall plan for obtaining answers to research questions (Polit and Beck 2012:58).

3.3 JUSTIFICATION FOR RESEARCH DESIGN

This study has used a qualitative research design that is descriptive and explorative to investigate factors that influence risk sexual behaviours among adolescent boys. The choice of this design has been informed by the fact that in qualitative research the design typically evolves over the course of the study. Qualitative studies use an emergent design that evolves as researchers make on going decision reflecting what has already been learned. An emergent design is not the result of laziness on the part of qualitative researchers but rather a reflection of their desire to have the inquiry based on the realities and view points of participants (Polit & Beck 2012:487).

This approach has allowed the researcher to interact with research participants in order to explore factors that influence risk sexual behaviours among adolescent boys in order to suggest recommendations for programming purposes. This approach has permitted the researcher to view findings in the context of participants' world view.

3.4 QUALITATIVE RESEARCH DESIGN

Qualitative research is an approach of naturalistic enquiry which is usually less obstructive than quantitative investigations. It aims to study the people in their social settings. The focus is on the meanings the participants in the study setting attach to their social world. It is the strength of qualitative research to study people in the field, in the natural setting. Qualitative research describes in words than in numbers (Bowling 2009:352). Qualitative research consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that make the world visible. Such practices turn the world into a series of representations, including field notes, interviews, conversations, recordings to the self. At this level, qualitative research involves an interpretive, naturalistic approach to the world (Creswell 2013: 43-44).

Furthermore, qualitative research begins with assumptions and use of theoretical frameworks that inform the study of research problems addressing the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a human problem. To study a problem, qualitative researchers use emerging qualitative approach enquiry, the collection of data in a natural setting sensitive to the people and places under study and data analysis that is both inductive and deductive and establishes patterns (Creswell 2013:44).

3.4.1 Common Characteristics of qualitative research design

In order to understand qualitative research design, it is important to be acquainted with common characteristics because these are factors that define qualitative research design. Creswell 2014:185-186 identifies the following core characteristics:

Natural Setting: Qualitative researchers tend to collect data in the field at the site where participants experience the problem under study. They do not bring individual participants into a laboratory (contrived situation), nor do they typically send out instruments for individuals to complete. This up-close information gathered by directly talking to people and seeing them behave within their context is a major characteristic of qualitative research. In the natural setting, the researchers have face to face interaction with the participants. In this study, the interviews and focus group discussions were conducted within children's home campus where participants spend their time and it was convenient to the research participants.

Researcher as a key instrument: Qualitative researchers collect data themselves through examining documents, observing behaviours or interviewing participants. They may use a protocol, an instrument for collecting data but the researchers are the ones who actually gather information. They tend not to use or rely on questionnaires or instruments designed by other researchers. In this study, the researcher made use of the interview guide developed by the researcher based on the aim, objectives, research questions and conceptual framework guiding this study.

Multiple sources of data: Qualitative researchers typically gather multiple forms of data, such as interviews, observations, documents and audio-visual rather than rely on a single data source. The researchers then review all the data, make sense of it and organize it into categories or themes that cut across the data sources. In this study the researcher made use of interviews, observations and discussions to collect data and has followed necessary processes to arrive at thematic categorization.

Complex reasoning through inductive and deductive logic (data analysis): Qualitative researchers build their patterns, categories and themes from bottom up by organising the data into increasingly more abstract units of information. This inductive

process illustrates working back and forth between themes and database until the researchers have established a comprehensive set of themes. Then deductively, the researchers look back at their data from themes to determine if more evidence can support each theme. As such, while the process begins inductively, deductive thinking also plays an important role as the analysis moves forward. The conclusions of this study were drawn from themes using the induction-deduction process.

Participants' meanings: Qualitative researchers keep focus on learning the meaning that the participants hold about the problem, not the meaning that the writers express in the literature. The findings of this study were based upon the meaning that the participants provided about the factors that influence risk sexual behaviours among adolescent boys.

Emergent design: The research process for qualitative researchers is emergent. This means that the initial plan for research cannot be tightly prescribed and that some of the phases may change when the researcher enters the field and begin to collect data. For example, questions may change, individuals studied and sites may be modified. The key idea behind the qualitative research is to learn about the problem from the participants and to address the research to obtain that information.

Reflexibility: In qualitative research, the inquirer reflects about how their role in the study and their personal background, culture and experiences hold potential for shaping their interpretations, such as themes they advance and the meaning they ascribe to the data. This aspect of the methods is more than merely advancing biases and values in the study, but how the background of the researchers can actually shape the direction of the study. In this study, the researcher made a pre and post reflection of her role, personal background on the study and have prevented and avoided biases thereof.

Holistic account: Qualitative researchers try to develop a complex picture of the problem under study. This involves multiple perspectives, identifying the many factors involved in a situation and generally sketching a larger picture that emerges. The findings and conclusions of this study were presented in such a way that they portrayed the picture of the problem studied.

3.4.2 Explorative design

Exploration is the attempt to develop an initial, rough understanding of a phenomenon. Much of social research is conducted to explore a problem. This approach typically occurs when a researcher examines a new interest or when the subject of study is relatively new (Babbie 2007:88). In this study, the researcher specifically explored the factors that influence risk sexual behaviours among adolescent boys aged 13-20 years in SOS Children's Village situated at Serowe in the Central district of Botswana.

3.4.3 Descriptive Design

Babbie (2007:89,115) allude that a description is the precise measurement and reporting of the characteristics of a phenomenon under study and that the researcher observes and describes what has been observed. In this study, the researcher observed adolescent boys aged 13-20 during the interviews and group discussions and described the participants in relation to the behaviours displayed during the sessions and has drawn conclusions.

3.4.4 Contextual design

A context is the circumstance that form the setting for an event or idea and in terms of which it can be understood. A context can also be described as a situation in which something that helps one to apprehend it. In this study, the context is adolescent boys risk sexual behaviours in SOS Children's Village-Serowe in Central district of Botswana.

3.5 RESEARCH METHODS

Research methods refer to the practices and techniques used to collect, process and analyse data, the sample size and methods of sampling (Bowling2009: 143). These are also the various procedures used in research. This section describes the methods that were used to conduct the study. These included the study setting, period, the population of study, the sampling and sampling techniques, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data

collection process and analysis, ethical considerations relevant to the study, rigor and trustworthiness of the study.

3.5.1 Research setting

Selecting a suitable and convenient research setting prior to data collection is paramount to research. This process helps to contextualize the study. Participants were recruited from SOS Children's Village in Serowe, Central District, Botswana. The Children's village admits orphans and vulnerable children from across Botswana depending on the availability of admission space, and whether the child meets the selection criteria of placement into the children's home or village. Children and adolescents who are under the custody of the children's village/ home are Botswana citizens from different ethnic groups. At the time of study, there were 150 children and adolescents enrolled at the SOS village, Serowe.

3.5.2 Recruitment Strategy

Recruitment is the process of selecting potential research participants. Identification, initial contact, screening and recruitment of potential human subjects form the foundation of informed consent process. The researcher had the responsibility to create a recruitment environment that was ethical and complying with the research regulations and guidance. Upon receiving the ethical clearance from Health Studies Higher Degrees Committee (HSHDC440/2015) of the University of South Africa (UNISA) (Annexure A), the researcher submitted the research proposal and application to SOS Children's Villages of Botswana requesting permission to conduct the study in the organization and to which the permission was obtained (Annexure B).

After receiving the permission from SOS Children's Village, the researcher then started recruitment of potential participants. The recruitment was done by means of selecting boys within the age range of the study who were taken through an introductory session about the aim and objectives of the study to gain their willingness and acceptance for participation in the study.

3.5.3 Population

A population is all the individuals or objects with common, defining characteristics (Polit & Beck 2012:59). Population is a study group by which the researcher wants to draw

conclusions (Babbie 2007:111). For the purpose of this study the population comprised of adolescents boys aged 13 to 20 years who reside at SOS Children's Village in Serowe, Botswana. The children's home enrolled 150 children and adolescents; 80 males aged 13-20 years, 20 boys aged 12 years and below; 35 girls aged 14 and below and 15 girls who were 15 years and below. Given the magnitude of boys in the children's home it was paramount for this study to explore factors influencing sexual risk behaviours for better and informed boys' sexual reproductive health programming. The participants of the study were admitted to the children's home or village for various reasons ranging from; adandonment, negligence by caregivers, orphanhood and abuse.

3.5.4 Sample and Sampling techniques

3.5.4.1 The Sample

A sample is a subset of a population (Bowling 2009:436; Polit & Beck 2012:59). It is a small part of the population that one wants to get information from (Verhoeven 2011:177). For this study, the sample comprised of adolescent boys aged 13-20 years living at SOS Children's Village or home in Serowe and who met the inclusion criteria and who were selected by means of purposive sampling technique.

3.5.4.2 Sampling method

Parahoo (2014:259) adds that sampling is a technique of selecting a sample that can be data representative of the population. There are two classes of sampling designs, namely: probability and non probability sampling. Probability sampling involves random selection of elements. In probability sampling, researchers can specify the probability that an element of the population will be included in the sample. In non probability sampling, elements are selected by non random methods. There is no way to estimate the probability that each element has been included in a non probability sample and every element usually does not have a chance for inclusion (Polit & Beck 2012:275). The researcher used a non probability sampling technique.

3.5.4.2.1 Non probability sampling

In non probability sampling method, the researcher determines the most typical characteristics that should be included in the sample. There are many types of non probability sampling, namely; convenience sampling, purposive sampling, quota sampling, expert sampling, chain.snowball sampling, heterogeneity sampling and maximum variation sampling. For the purpose of this study, the researcher adopted purposive sampling as a relevant sampling technique to recruit adolescent boys who were subject the study.

3.5.4.2.1.1 Purposive Sampling

According to Kumar (2011:207), in purposive sampling, the researcher based on his/her knowledge her/him about the population, judges as to who can provide best information that is detailed to achieve the objectives of the study. Only boys who were within the ages 13-20 and who were willing to participate in the study were selected. They expressed their views relating to factors that influence risk sexual behaviours among boys.

3.5.4.3 Sample Size

For a qualitative study, a small sample size may lead to inadequate richness. However, the number of participants is adequate when saturation is reached. Data saturation according to Saumure & Given (2014:3 is the point in data collection when no new or relevant information emerges with respect to the current subject of study. The researcher used an interview guide for 4 focus groups (made of 7 participants) and one on one interviews (12 participants) and saturation was reached by the 30th participant and for better understanding of the subject the researcher continued with interviews up to the 40th participant.

To ensure a smooth selection of the sample, the researcher developed a criteria which allowed the participants to take part in the study or to be excluded from the study.

3.5.5 INCLUSION CRITERIA

These are a set of predefined characteristics used to identify subjects who will be included in the research study. Inclusion criteria along with exclusion criteria make up

the selection used to rule in or out the target population for a research study. Inclusion should respond to the scientific objective of the study and are critical to accomplish it (Velasco 2010:3).

The inclusion criteria assist the researcher in choosing the sample of study. The target population of this study met the following criteria:

- A male adolescent aged between 13-20 years
- Living in SOS Children's Village in Serowe
- Ability to communicate in Setswana or English
- Willingness to participate in the study

3.5.6 EXCLUSION CRITERIA

For this study, the following were excluded from the study:

- Male adolescents below 12 years old and older than 20 years of age
- Male adolescents not able to communicate in Setswana or English
- Male adolescents not willing to participate
- Male adolescents not living in SOS Children's Village in Serowe

3.5.7 Data collection

Data collection is the process of getting permission, conducting a good qualitative sampling strategy, developing means of recording information both digitally and on paper, sorting the data, and anticipating ethical issues that may arise (Creswell 2013:145). Data collection enables the researcher to answer stated research questions hence consequently achieving the objectives of the study. For the purposes of this study, focus group discussions and one on one interviews were used to collect data. The interviews and discussions were audio taped and filed notes were taken during the sessions.

3.5.7.1 Data collection instrument

A self-developed interview guide was used as the instrument for collecting data. The advantages of interviews include direct observation of responses of the subject, opportunities to clarify questions if misunderstood, and ability to ask questions can be at several levels to get the most information from the subject (Burns & Grove, 2011). An interview guide was developed and comprised of the main question and probing questions. The interview guide was based on the aim, objectives and research questions. The interview guide was then sent to the researcher's supervisor for validation and approval. After the guide was approved, the guide was ready for use (Annexure C).

3.5.7.2 Pre-testing the interview guide

The researcher pre-tested the interview guide in order to test the participants' understanding of the main question and to check the kind of information that would be gathered. This was done with two participants who were selected by means of purposive sampling technique and who met the inclusion criteria. These two participants did not take part in the study. The main question was found to be sufficient as it allowed participants to relate their views on factors that influence risk sexual behaviours among boys.

3.5.7.3 Data collection processes

3.5.7.3.1 Tasks related to data collection

The researcher has performed the following tasks related to data collection process:

- The researcher selected research participants and communicated with participants about focus group and interview sessions
- The researcher maintained research controls as laid out in the research design

3.5.7.3.2 Data Collection steps

Data collection was done in the following phases:

- **First step:** This entails obtaining the certificate of ethical clearance from University of South Africa.
- **Second step:** This phase is when permission was sought from SOS Children's Villages of Botswana to conduct a study in their Serowe Children's home
- **Third step:** This phase include gathering of information on the research method, writing the interview guide and all the preparation concerning the commencement of the study at the identified setting.
- **Fourth step:** This phase includes inteviews and discussions held for data collection, recording and analyzing inteviews and discussions during data gathering.
- **Firth step:** This is the last phase which marked the end of study on field and this was done only when data saturation was reached.

3.5.7.3.3 Data Collection techniques

The study was conducted in SOS Children's Village and only adolescent boys who met the inclusion criteria took part in the study. Data was collected by means of semi structured inteviews and focus group discussions using an interview guide. Data collection was scheduled and carried out during the agreed period from 5 to 15 January 2016. To ensure privacy and confidentiality, the inteviews and discussions were conducted in a private office within the SOS Children's home and it was convenient for the participants and the researcher.

The researcher provides a brief description of some types of interview inorder to enhance the appropriateness of chosing semi structured inteviews as well as focus group discussions.

3.5.7.3.3.1 Inteviews

An interview is a conversation in which the inteviwee's pereceptions are paramount. The aim is to gather information about a particular subject. Inteviews normally take the form of a dialogue between inteviwee and interviewer. Inteviews are advantagerous in that they allow participants to describe what is meaningful in their own expressions and

require a trained interviewer to ensure that the interview uncover interesting ideas and themes relevant to the study.

3.5.7.3.3.2 Types of interviews

There are many types of interviews, namely; face to face, structured, and semi structured interviews (Bowling 2009:311). However, for the purpose of this study semi structured interview was found to be relevant as discussed below.

3.5.7.3.3.2.1 Semi structured interviews

A semi structured interview is a one on one method of data collection that involves the interviewer and interviewee discussing specific topics in depth. It can be described as a conversation with purpose. Semi structured interview typically uses an interview protocol that serves as a guide. Once the interview has started the interviewee has more say in the process (Hayes & Stratton 2012: 239). The advantage of using semi structured interview is that the researcher gains in-depth information and acquires information on sensitive topics (Hinnik, Hutte & Bailey 2011:131). The authors, further outline the disadvantages of using semi-structured interviews as:

- A lot of transcription is needed
- Flexibility is needed in accordance with how the interviewee story
- One needs skill to establish rapport, use motivational probes
- One to one interview do not allow feedback from others

The researcher conducted the interviews and established rapport with participants before the real questioning started. Participants were comfortable and the interviews took place. The research was non judgemental and showed respect to the participant throughout the interviews. The researcher listened carefully to the discussions and narration.

3.5.7.3.3.1 Focus group discussions

In this study, focus group discussion consisting of seven adolescent boys were conducted using the interview guide and the technique was appropriate and relevant in

that it allowed adolescent boys to discuss the problem of study amongst themselves with the guidance of the researcher. The focus group discussions are an advantage because:

- the dynamics interaction among participants stimulates their thoughts and reminds them of their own feelings about the research topic
- all participants including the researcher have an opportunity to ask questions and these produce more information than individual interviews

In this study four focus group discussions were conducted in the private room in the children's home (each group at a time). The participants were made comfortable and introduced to the sessions and the researcher managed the group dynamics that showed up during the discussions.

3.5.7.3.3.2 Other data collection instrument and methods

- **Researcher as a data collection instrument:** Before and after the interviews, it was important that the researcher considered and reflected how her role as the interviewer impacted on the research process. The researcher followed ethics of research throughout the study.
- **Field notes:** These are written notes on descriptive account of what the researcher heard, saw, felt and observed during the course of interviews and discussions. Shorthand was used to sketch the notes and later made tail with the help of the audio recordings that were done per session. The participants observed and captured the body language, reaction, language and the mood of participants during the course of data collection.
- **Audio recording:** The recording of discussions ensured accuracy of information and it allowed the researcher to listen to the participants' expressions and meanings. Permission was sought from the participants to use the audio recorder and it was placed in a way that it could not distract the proceedings of the interviews and discussions.
- **Reflexive thought:** Reflexivity is a strategy to help ensure that the over involvement of the researcher is not a threat to the credibility of this study. In this context, reflexivity is the assessment of the influence of the researcher's background, her perceptions, experiences and interest during the research (Chilisa & Preece 2005:168). The researcher developed a reflective journal

which assisted her to reflect and introspect on her perceptions and it helped the researcher to create transparency in the research process. The use of reflective journal enabled the researcher to make her own experiences, thoughts, opinions and feelings visible.

- **Reasoning strategies:** The researcher used the process of reasoning to organise and draw conclusions. The relevant reasoning strategies to this study include inductive and deductive reasoning. Inductive reasoning moves from the specific to the general, where particular instances are observed and then combined into larger statement (Babbie 2007:22). Inductive reasoning was used to draw conclusions from the themes and sub themes that emerged during the discussions held with the adolescent boys in this study. Deductive reasoning moves from the general to the specific. It moves from a pattern that might be logically expected to the expected pattern actually occurs (Babbie 2007:22).
- **Synthesis:** De Vos (2002:337) defines synthesis as a process of building up separate elements of ideas into connected wholes. The researcher has used synthesis to identify the relationship between themes, concepts and thereby examining the study results taking into account the motivation of the study as well as the literature review conducted.
- **Description:** This is the process whereby the researcher gives a detailed discussion of characteristics and establishes relationships between themes and sub themes. The researcher described themes as well as the research setting. The researcher attempted to share the participants view points in reference to the factors that influence adolescent boys sexual risk behaviours in SOS Children's Village, Serowe.

3.6 DATA ANALYSIS

Data management in qualitative research is reductionist in nature; it involves converting masses of data into smaller, manageable segments, it is putting those segments together in a meaningful way (Polit & Beck 2012:562). Data analysis in qualitative research consists of preparing and organising the data for analysis, then reducing the

data into themes through the process of coding and condensing the codes and finally representing data into figures, tables or discussions (Creswell 2013:180). In this study, reading through transcripts and jotting down ideas and categorizing them into prominent themes. The transcribed data verbatim assisted the researcher during the careful analysis that was conducted in this research. Thematic data analysis was used as described in Polit and Beck (2012:562). Thematic analysis provided structure and guided the development of meaning to the raw data. The researcher developed thematic areas simultaneously with data collection and the researcher further made use of Colaizzi's seven steps of analysis Polit & Beck 2014:309).

3.6.1 Data analysis according to Colaizzi's seven steps

The researcher familiarized herself with data by reading field notes and listening to audio recordings hence doing some data analysis for initial understanding of data meaning. Transcription of data was done verbatim.

Table 3.6.1.2 Data analysis according to Colaizzi's seven steps

Colaizzi's steps of data analysis	Data analysis activities in this study
1 To acquire a feeling for the protocols, the researcher started reading the protocols from the transcripts several times (Polit & Beck 2014: 309)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The researcher read all the verbatim transcripts many times
2 As each written data is read, significant statements are extracted (Polit & Beck 2014: 309)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reading data several times enabled the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of the transcripts, to extract noteworthy statements
3 New meanings of each noteworthy statement were formulated (Polit & Beck 2014: 309)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New meanings from significant statements were attached to the participants statements
4 Formulated meanings should be organized into themes and sub themes; -It was vital to validate these themes by	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Themes and sub themes were formulated and validated in reference to the original protocols

referring back to the protocols -Discrepancies between clusters were noted and the temptation to ignore themes that did not fit was ignored (Polit& Beck 2014: 309).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examination of various sections was done to find similarities and differences in the data • All themes were taken into consideration
5 Integrate results into an indepth description of the phenomenon under study (Polit& Beck 2014: 309).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The phenomenon of factors influencing sexual risk factors among adolescent boys was described
6 Writing and re-writing themes and sub-themes to further verify the findings (Polit& Beck 2012: 556).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was documentation and this allowed a deeper interpretation of themes and sub themes
7 On going probing and validation of findings with participants (Polit& Beck 2014: 591).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Probing was done throughout data collection process and it was to ensure accuracy of the meaning.

3.7 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

A series of ethical issues were taken into consideration during this study. A discussion of those issues is provided hereunder in order to recognise the compliance of this study to research ethics. According to Polit and Beck (2012:150), when human beings are used as study participants, care must be exercised to ensure that their rights are protected. The researcher adopted three principles of the Belmont Report, namely beneficence, respect for human dignity as well as justice (Polit & Beck 2012:152).

3.7.1 Clearance and permission

The researcher was granted permission and approval to conduct the study from the University of South Africa (Research Ethics Committee-Department of Health Studies) (Annexure A) and SOS Children's Villages of Botswana (Annexure B).

3.7.2 Obtaining consent and assent

The objectives, significance and purpose of study were explained to the participants in detail. The researcher explained this in both English and Setswana and the main emphasis was be around the fact that participants are not obliged to take part in the study if they are not comfortable to do so. A written consent form was explained and presented to the participant who chose to take part for completion. The researcher assured the participants of their protection and that the information they provided was not going to be used against them. The researcher treated participants as autonomous entities by giving them a voluntary opportunity to make a decision to participate in the study or not. No adolescent boy was disregarded or coerced for non-participation and were assisted to make an informed consent with full understanding of the purpose of the study. The researcher sensitively respected the participants' beliefs, habits, lifestyles, culture and emotions as each contribution was received without judging or condemning participants. Confidentiality of participants was assured.

The study participants younger than 18 years required the consent of their legal guardians. The researcher explained the purpose, significance and objective of the study to the guardians of the concerned children, being SOS Children's Village of Botswana and thereafter presented a consent and acceptance form to the release of minors selected as study participants.

3.7.3 Voluntary participation

The researcher had informed the participants that their participation in the study was voluntary and that if during the course of the interview, they wish to withdraw they could do so without providing reasons. The participants were informed of this right before interviews and discussions. Participants were also informed that they were free to refuse answering any question they wish not to attempt to. The participants were assured that information collected during sessions will not be identified with them.

3.7.4 Confidentiality and participants'right to autonomy

The researcher assured participants that information gathered during interviews and discussions would be treated with sensitivity and rendered confidential. Data would be kept safe and their names will not reflect in the study report. The researcher put the transcripts and recording in a lockable cabinet where she was the only one accessing the cabinet. Soft report was stored in a password protected computer.

3.7.5 Participants' right to self determination

The participants were advised that they were free to express themselves without fear for victimisation. Participants and the researcher respected each other during data collection sessions.

3.7.6 Participants rights to privacy

The researcher assured participants that under no circumstances the research report become particular to the participants of the study. The sessions were held in a private room where participants were free to participate.

3.7.7 Participants rights to fair treatment

The researcher ensured that all participants who met the inclusion criteria took part in the study and no one was excluded from the study on the basis of their origin, race, ethnicity, culture and language.

3.7.8 Avoidance of harm

The researcher made efforts to ensure the safety of the participants during the course of the study. As far as data collection is concerned no harm occurred.

3.7.9 Responsibility to seek advice

The researcher reached out to the research supervisor during instances of uncertainty with research processes and appropriateness of research methods.

3.8 Ensuring scientific rigour

Holloway and Wheeler (2002:251) define rigour as “the means by which we show integrity”. To ensure rigour, the researcher carried out peer debrief, triangulation of data collection methods, audit trail, and description of the target population and data collection methods. The researcher followed a set of principles to ensure ethical conduct as discussed in the next section.

3.8.1 Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness is the degree of confidence and integrity the qualitative researchers have in their data and it is assessed using the criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability and comformability (Polit & Beck 2014:394)

3.8.2 Credibility

According to Polit and Beck (2012:584), credibility is viewed by Lincoln and Guba (1985) as an over-riding goal of qualitative research, it refers to the confidence in the truth of the data and interpretations of them. The following steps ensured credibility:

- Prolonged involvement: this refers to investing sufficient time to learn culture and build trust. The researcher has previously worked for 2 years as social worker in a similar setting and therefore the rapport and trust was smoothly established.
- Triangulation of different methods: According to Poli & Beck 2014: 543), triangulation of different methods involves using multiple methods of data collection to investigate the same phenomenon or concept. The researcher conducted individual interviews and focus group discussions with participants. Observations and perspectives were drawn during these sessions.
- Data capturing: Interviews and discussions were audio recorded and field notes transcribed verbatim.
- Debriefing: In debriefing sessions, researchers presented written summaries of the data and emerging themes of the study. The supervisor of this research study continuously asked questions about different aspects of the study and cross examining the authenticity and accuracy of the account and for objective assessment of the study.

3.8.3 Dependability

Lincoln and Guba's (1985) framework defines dependability as the stability of data over time and conditions. The researcher made trail audit in the form of audio recordings and interview transcripts by which reference can be made to if need be. Moreover, the researcher was focused, as well as being objective in data collection, analysis and reporting. The researcher reported in detail the study processes undertaken in the study. The findings of this study were made open to scrutiny by the supervisor of this research.

3.8.4 Confirmability

According to Polit and Beck (2012:585), confirmability refers to the potential for congruence between two or more people about data accuracy, relevance and meaning. The researcher ensured that the findings of the study are the result of the research and not the researcher's assumptions and preconceptions. Confirmability entails neutrality which is the freedom from bias during the research process and results description. In this study, the researcher conducted focus group discussions and one on one interviews which ensure that participants voices were reflected in the findings (Polit & Beck 2014:585) The researcher combined methods of data collection such as field notes, audio recordings, interviewing and checking findings with the participants.

3.8.5 Transferability

Transferability refers to the degree to which the findings from the data can be transferred to other settings under similar conditions (Polit & Beck 2014: 585). The researcher used informative descriptions of data in the research report so that readers of the report can evaluate the applicability of the data to other contexts.

3.9 CONCLUSION

This chapter has highlighted the methodology, and that includes the approach, design, population, sample, data management, analysis and the ethical considerations for the study. In the next chapter the study findings will be presented in accordance with the thematic areas of data collection in order to respond to the research questions under investigation.

CHAPTER 4

ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION AND DESCRIPTION OF FINDINGS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Qualitative methods were used in this study and this chapter presents major findings of the factors that influence sexual risk behaviours among adolescent boys. The study aimed at exploring the factors influencing adolescent boys sexual risk behaviour in order to inform programming for youth in this subject of interest.

Chapter 3 discussed the research designs and methodology that were used during the implementation of this study. This chapter focuses the findings from the qualitative methods of data collected from adolescent boys aged 13-20 years.

4.2 DATA ANALYSIS

In qualitative research data analysis is described as an inductive process that involves putting units together in a pattern that conveys meaning (Polit & Beck 2014:304). Colaizzi's as described in (Polit & Beck 2012: 566) guided the the thematic development and analysis.

Individual and focus group interviews or discussions were conducted for forty participants. Four focus group discussions were held consisting of seven participants. Twelve additional participants were interviewed one on one. Four main themes emerged from the conversation or discussion held with participants. The identified themes and sub themes added knowledge and understanding of the subject under study. Data collection and analysis occurred concurrently as in the process of data analysis, interpretation of data also took place.

4.3 RESEARCH FINDINGS

The presentation of the findings begins with the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants followed by the thematic analysis of participants' narrations with the aim of meeting the study objectives.

4.3.1 Demographic information of the participants (n=40)

The 40 participants were all blacks, in particular Botswana nationals, male adolescents of different educational levels. The boys differed in terms of age, levels of education, ethnic group as well as religions as reflected in the tables below.

4.3.1.1 Age

Table 4.1 The distribution of participants in terms of their age

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
13-14	8	20%
15-16	12	30%
17-18	11	27.5%
19-20	9	22.5%
TOTAL	40	100%

This table shows that 8 participants were between 13-14 years, 12 participants were aged between 15-16 years old, 11 participants were in the ages 17 and 18 years and 9 participants were in the age range of 19-20 years old.

4.3.1.2 Level of education

Table 4.2 The distribution of participants in terms of their education level

LEVEL OF EDUCATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Grade 8-9	12	30%
Grade 10-11	14	35%
Grade 12 to vocational training	14	35%
TOTAL	40	100%

This tables shows that all the participants were still school going although they vary with the different levels of formal education.

4.3.1.3 Ethnic group

Table 4.3 The distribution of participants in terms of their ethnic groups.

ETHNIC GROUP	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Bangwato	9	22.5%
Basarwa	8	20%
Bakalaka	8	20%
Bakwena	7	17.5%
Batawana	8	20%
Total	40	100

This table shows that 9 participants were Bangwato, 8 participants were Basarwa, another 8 participants were Bakalaka, 7 participants were Bakwena and 8 participants were Batawana.

4.3.1.4 Religion

Table 4.4 The distribution of participants in terms of their religion

RELIGION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
African traditional Religion	7	17.5%
Christianity	31	77.5%
Islam	2	5%
TOTAL	40	100%

This table shows that 7 participants were followers of African traditional religion, 31 participants were Christians and 2 were Muslims.

4.4 THEMES AND SUB THEMES

From data analysis, four themes emerged with sub-themes presented in table 4.5 below.

The identified themes during the data analysis are:

- Substance and alcohol use
- Peer pressure
- Lack of knowledge
- Domestic violence

Table 4.5 A summary of themes and sub-themes that emerged prominently in the study

THEMES	SUB-THEMES
<p>Theme 1 Substance and alcohol use</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unprotected sex
<p>Theme 2 Peer Pressure</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experimentation • Multiple sexual partners
<p>Theme 3 Lack of knowledge</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sexual matters regarded as taboo
<p>Theme 4 Domestic violence</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anger displacement

This table presents all the views of the themes and sub themes generated from the data.

4.5 FINDINGS AND LITERATURE PROTOCOL

4.5.1 THEME 1: SUBSTANCE AND ALCOHOL USE

Participants were asked to give their understanding of sexual risk behaviours and factors that influence it. On the basis of the participants response to this main question the theme of substance and alcohol use emerged. Participants reported that substance

and alcohol influence boys to take part in risky sexual behavior such as unprotected sex which is presented below as a sub theme.

4.5.1.1 SUB THEME: UNPROTECTED SEX

The following quotations provide evidence of the participants understanding of sexual risk behaviours:

“I understand risk sexual behaviour as the way someone behaves putting themselves on risk of getting infected with HIV”

“I know that risk sexual behaviour is when I have sex without a condom”

“Alcohol and the use of drugs such as marijuana during pens down parties make most of us to end up sleeping with girls without a condom because we will be drunk

“Even though these guys are saying unprotected sex is a risk, it is very enjoyable when one is drunk...at least – fro- (meaning a girl) will not notice when you are shy especially for the first time you have sex”

Participants reveals that unprotected sex is a sexual behaviour which at times is perpetuated by the use of substance as per the above quotations. According to Hall, Holmqvist and Sherry (2004:4), risky sexual behaviours can take many forms ranging from multi sexual partners, unprotected sex and engaging in sexual intercourse under the influence of alcohol or substance. There are five major contributing factors related to risky sexual behaviours: substance use, gender roles, peer influences, parental involvement, and level of knowledge and information on sex, STIs and HIV and AIDS (Lee, Cintron & Kotcher 2014:414). Abuse of alcohol or drugs in the family increases the chances that teens will have sex more frequently and with more partners (Kirby & Lepore 2007:6-7).

4.5.2 THEME 2: PEER PRESSURE

Peer influence or pressure has emerged as a major theme with connectedness to two sub-themes, namely, experimentation of sex and multiple sexual partners. Participants

reported that the choices they make pertaining to unsafe sexual practices is influenced by ones peers to conform to what they do as a way of maintain peer alliance.

4.5.2.1 Sub-Theme: Experimentation

Participants alluded the following statements with regards to experimentation:

"I learnt to have sex when I was doing form 1 and my friends taught me; I also wanted to experience it"

"A real dude / boy must know how it feels to have sex otherwise that boy will be stupid"

"Most of us gents want to please each other; we teach each other a lot of things like how to propose a girl, how to have sex, we go to parties and do a lot of things together"

"It is embaracing for people to think that you do not have a penis only because you are unable to experiment sex"

"Majita aa go zonda ha o sa tshware cheri"- this means boys will dislike you if you do not have sex with a girl.

Peer pressure has been identified as an influencing factor of high risk sexual behaviour among young people. This assertion is supported by various scholars as cited in Dekeke and Sandy (2014:22). Kirby and Lepore (2007:123) state that "peer pressure encourages youth to experiment a range of sexual behaviours and doing so may lead to increased risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases including HIV/AIDS". Thupayagale-Tshweneagae (2010:56) observes that "the influence of peer pressure on such risk behaviour is probably because youths have the potential to internalise the opinions of their peers and externalise the same in the presence of the sexual partners. This discussion shows that at an interpersonal level, peer pressure influences behaviour development.

Grobler et al (2007:32) also highlighted that the sexual drive for experimentation in adolescents has the potential to place adolescents at risk of unprotected sexual activity.

4.5.2.2 Sub Theme 2: Multiple sexual partners

According to participants, the practice of multiple sexual partners is a risky sexual behaviour contributed by the influence of those who view the practice as noble.

Reporting of multiple sexual partnerships was more common among males than among females (Doyle et al 2012:796).

Participants reported that:

“It shows that I am a real guy if I have many sexual partners”

“It is pride for me to be loved by many girls you know”

“All these guys know that it is super to be having more than one girl”

Multiple sexual partners is evidently emerged as a common risky sexual behaviour among adolescent boys.

4.5.3 THEME 3: LACK OF KNOWLEDGE

The third theme that emerged was lack of knowledge. One sub theme was discussed in line with the stated theme:

4.5.3.1 Sub theme: Sexual matters regarded as a taboo

Melles (2009:1) asserts that there is no formal sex education in schools in Botswana, and that many parents are uncomfortable talking about sexuality with their children. However, young people receive some information about sexuality and HIV prevention both informally from friends and acquaintances, and through Botswana's HIV prevention social marketing programs (Melles 2009:1).

Participants reported the following:

“Sometimes we do these bad or risky things because no one guides us”

“I get my counsel on sexual matters from my friends who apparently are doing the same risky practices”

“I don't discuss sex related matters with anyone except my friends”

4.5.4 THEME 3: DOMESTIC VIOLENCE

The fourth theme that emerged was domestic violence. One sub theme is discussed, namely, anger displacement.

4.5.4.1 Sub theme: Anger displacement

Participants revealed that their living circumstances have contributed to the act of coercing sexual activity with girls. They explained that having seen their older siblings (girls) who apparently play a caregiver role, being abused by their boyfriends in the home angered them hence their revenge in manipulating younger girls in the community.

The next chapter will therefore present the conclusions and recommendations of this qualitative study.

4.4 CONCLUSION

In accordance with the objectives of the study it is notable that adolescent boys' involvement in risky sexual behaviours is accounted for by the social and interpersonal network that exists around them. This involves their interaction with family members, friends, school community, access to media materials on sex education as well as the ability of each individual adolescent to exercise control over what they do with regards to sexual practices. Every person has a sense of control or skill which is obviously influenced either negatively or positively by the social entities such as family, peers, substance use, traditional norms or cultural practices as well the education information that young people acquire in various social arenas like social media, social clubs and television broadcasts.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION OF MAJOR FINDINGS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter will focus on the discussion of the main research findings, incorporating the data obtained from participants. The study aimed at exploring the factors influencing adolescent boys sexual risk behaviour. The discussion of the major research findings will be within the context of the participants' own understanding and explanation of their subjective experiences as well as the meanings they create about sexual risk behaviours among boys.

The emphasis will be placed on a discussion of

- Substance and alcohol use
- Peer pressure
- Lack of knowledge
- Domestic violence

5.1.1 SUBSTANCE AND ALCOHOL ABUSE

In this study, most of the participants believe that drinking increases the likelihood of sexual activity, enhances sexual experience, and promotes riskier sexual behaviour. Young people sometimes attribute risky sexual experiences to the fact that they were drinking and report drinking. According to Ondrej (2012:12), empirical research has generally supported this idea, with alcohol consumption being positively related to engaging in high-risk sexual behaviours (Leigh & Stall, 1993) including deciding not to use condoms (Conner et al., 1999) and engaging in casual sex (Conner & Flesch, 2001). These types of behaviour are more likely to occur when one or both sexual partners are under the influence of alcohol or drugs (Cooper, 2006; Parkes et al., 2007). Moreover, Ondrej (2012:12) states that a study by MacDonald (1996) found that alcohol decreases the likelihood of condom use during casual sex. Also binge-drinking teens have been found approximately three times less likely to use condoms, and recent marijuana users are almost two times less likely to use condoms (Tapert et al., 2001). The use of marijuana, cocaine or other illicit drugs by adolescents has been shown to be associated with increased rates of sexual intercourse in general, having multiple

sexual partners and lower rates of condom use, particularly for users of illicit stimulant drugs (Lowry et al., 1994) in Ondrej (2012:12). The community a teen lives in influences his or her sexual behaviour. In particular, adolescents who live in disorganised communities; those with higher rates of substance abuse, violence, and hunger are more likely to begin having sex early (Kirby & Lepore 2007:6-7).

Alcohol and substance abuse as reported by the participants is one of the main contributing factors adolescent boys sexual risk behaviours. It is imperative to note that sexual activities carried out under the influence of alcohol and any behaviour modifying substance presents a sexual risk opportunity for unprotected sex. Literature concurs with the deliberations of the male adolescents who participated in this current study.

5.1.2 PEER PRESSURE

Peer influence is a critical social factor that impacts the lives of adolescents. During adolescence, peers become a crucial source of modelling, reinforcement, and support concerning their own behaviour, value and beliefs system. The results of a study by Ntshwarang & Malinga-Musamba (2015:106-109) indicate that adolescents tend to listen more, and practice, what their peers say or do. Therefore, in order to develop measures that are culturally sensitive to adolescents, there is a need to use adolescents in developing and disseminating such messages. Ondrej (2012:15) cites the following evidence affirming the role that peer pressure plays into sexual risk behaviour;

It was repeatedly found that involvement with deviant peer groups (e.g. using alcohol and drug use or being delinquent) was related to the participation in high risk sexual practices (Metzler et al., 1994; Miller et al., 2000).

In addition, a study by Scaramella (1998) showed that deviant peer affiliations comprised a strong pathway to sexual risk in the overall model of adolescent sexual risk behaviour. Peers during adolescence are the preferential sources of information about sexuality. Therefore, their behavior may serve as reference norm for others with high potential of impact (Potard et al., 2008). The perception of their peers on the subject of sexual behaviours is an important normative predictor of intention (Hollander, 2001) with regard to the beginning of sexual relations and engaging in sexuality. Peer influence came up as one of the major contributors to risk sexual behaviours. Despite sex education obtained from male relatives, schools guidance lessons, participants

confirmed that the choices they make in the adolescence stage are mostly influenced by their peer alliances. They reported that what they learn from their peers is mostly what they do because they want to retain their peer alliance identity, they do not want to lose friends and that they discuss most of these subjects together whereas they do not feel comfortable to discuss with adults.

It was also revealed during group discussions that boys would like to affiliate to a particular peer group as such if one decides to go against any practise by the group he may be dismissed from the group and this is an unlikely mishap which none of them would like. They would not want to lose friends so they live to the values and practices of the peer group. Theoretically it has been proven that adolescents (boys and girls) undergo a psychological crisis of identity and role confusion. In a case where, an adolescent does not receive positive social support, it is possible that they do not resolve the developmental crisis successfully hence leading to unacceptable or risky behaviours learnt through negative peer pressure. It was also notable that some peer alliances influence acceptable behaviours such as the use of condoms and non-indulgence in drug or substance use.

Literature provides evidence that sex experimentation among adolescent boys as well as the practice of multiple sexual partners as risky sexual behaviours emanating from the influence of peers. Kirby and Lepore (2007:7) report that teens are more likely to have sex if their best friends and peers are older, use alcohol or drugs, or engage in other negative behaviour. Similarly, they are more likely to have sex if they believe their friends have permissive values about sex, or are actually having sex. If teens believe their friends support condom use or actually use condoms, chances are greater that they will use condoms themselves. This discussion shows that at an interpersonal level, peer pressure influences behaviour development and learning.

5.1.3 LACK OF KNOWLEDGE

Even though parents discourage adolescents' risky sexual behaviours, findings indicate that they do not discuss with them issues of sex and sexuality in detail. This, therefore, undermines efforts to address HIV and AIDS risk behaviours.

The qualitative findings of a study by Ntshwarang and Malinga-Musamba (2015:106) demonstrated that adolescents are influenced by behavioural, normative and control

beliefs to engage in risky sexual behaviours. There were myths that were identified that adolescents adhere to. Such myths include having multiple partners to strengthen manhood, and suffering from virgin disease and painful erection due to lack of sexual intercourse. The study by Ntshwarang and Malinga-Musamba (2015:106) conclude the following:

- Adolescents' sexual behaviour in contemporary Botswana is still highly influenced by traditional and cultural ways of communication. For example, oral communication tools such as proverbs and metaphorical language can contribute negatively or positively towards adolescents' sexual health.
- The negative factors include proverbs and metaphorical language as drivers of adolescents increased vulnerability to HIV and oral communication as a significant factor in influencing adolescents' early sexual debut. From a positive point of view, oral communication tools can be used as educational materials to help adolescents learn how the misinterpretation of cultural communication can expose them to risky sexual behaviours.

Moreover, Melles (2009:1) asserts that there is no formal sex education in schools in Botswana, and that many parents are uncomfortable talking about sexuality with their children. However, young people receive some information about sexuality and HIV prevention both informally from friends and acquaintances, and through Botswana's HIV prevention social marketing programs. For the purposes of this study, it emerges explicitly that ignorance or lack of knowledge contributes to sexual risk behaviours.

Lack of guidance refers to unavailability of a guardian/parent to support or provide life skill education in the home setting. Participants of this study alluded that they get education on sexuality related matters from school in their guidance and counselling lessons, male cousins, uncles or relatives. They further stated that from their social backgrounds, it is culturally unacceptable to engage a female custodian or guardian on matters of sex education with a boy child. Family is a very important aspect of human development. If young adolescents do not get guidance at home, then it places them at a risk of learning 'street behaviours' that are unacceptable behaviours practiced outside family environment. Family values are believed to account for moulding every individual from childhood to adulthood hence the need for positive parenting or care giving in the

home environment. In the traditional context of Botswana, it is common for some cultural stereotype guardians and parents to prohibit discussions on sexual behaviours/practises with boys in particular unless it comes as a disciplinary precaution applied prior to a boy who impregnated a girl. Such education could be accessed at rites of passage such as *bojale* (initiation school for girls) and *bogwera* (initiation school for boys) which are rare these days. Therefore, this finding is in congruence with the already cited literature which answers the research questions of this study.

5.1.4 DOMESTIC VIOLENCE

The community a teen lives in influences his or her sexual behaviour. In particular, teens or adolescents who live in disorganised communities; those with higher rates of substance abuse, violence, and hunger are more likely to begin having sex early. Family circumstances are very important in determining risk (Kirby & Lepore 2007:6-7). Teens or adolescents who live with both parents and enjoy close relationships with them are less likely to have unprotected sex and become pregnant. According to Kirby and Lepore (2007:6-7) a majority of studies finds that teens living with both parents are less likely to become pregnant (or cause a pregnancy) or to give birth (or father a child). Family income is also a factor: the majority of studies found that teens in families with higher incomes were less likely to become pregnant or to bear children (Kirby & Lepore 2007:6-7).

These findings regarding parents' education and income may reflect the emphasis that many such parents place on obtaining an education, pursuing a career, and avoiding early childbearing, as well as, to some extent, the greater resources available to support teens in these pursuits. If teens experience considerable parental support and feel connected to their parents, they are less likely to initiate sex at an early age, and they have sex less frequently. If parents monitor and supervise their teens appropriately, the teens are likely to have fewer sexual partners than if parents do not monitor them (or, according to atleast one study, if parents monitor them excessively). At the extreme, if teens have been maltreated and physically abused by their families, then they are much more likely to have sex at an early (Kirby & Lepore 2007:6-7).

Abuse of alcohol or drugs in the family increases the chances that teens will have sex more frequently and with more partners (Kirby & Lepore 2007:6-7). They assert two possible reasons for this effect: family substance abuse may encourage young people to drink and use drugs themselves, which can lead to more frequent sex with more partners, or family substance abuse may simply be a marker for more general family dysfunction, which can lead to sexual risk taking by adolescents. Similarly, teens whose older siblings model early sex or childbearing are more likely to have early sex themselves.

Participants of this study revealed that their living circumstances have contributed to the act of coercing sexual activity with girls. Some of the participants explained that having seen their older siblings (girls) who apparently play a caregiver role, being abused by their boyfriends in their natural homes angered them hence their revenge in manipulating younger girls in the community. This practice is not only a health hazard but also a legal offence, which leads to juvenile delinquency. It also exposes the girl child to sexual violence, which hampers their personality development. It emerged that anger displacement in the form sexual exploitation of younger girls by male adolescents was influenced by the lived experiences of prolonged exposure of boys to domestic violence and family dysfunction. An observation made by the researcher is that participants perceive sexual exploitation of younger girls as vengeance for traumatic caregiver violence they got exposed to. According to this discussion, literature confirms that a dysfunctional family presents a breeding arena for angry and hopeless children.

5.1.5 CONCLUSION

Social variables such as substance and alcohol use, peer influence or pressure, lack of knowledge and domestic violence were found as factors influencing sexual risk behaviour among adolescent boys. Safer initiation of sexual life seems to be associated with safer sexual practices later in life. Interventions focusing on healthy sexual behavior are needed. Based on the data from this study, the researcher advocates for interventions aimed at adolescent boys way before sexual initiation takes place. Study findings show that show the need for health promotion programmes in early boys' adolescence. The findings of this study are henceforth supported in literature.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this study was to explore factors associated with sexual risk behaviours among adolescent boys in Serowe, Botswana. This chapter therefore draws conclusions from the findings, and these provide answers to the objectives of the study as stipulated in Chapter 1.

The possible limitations of the study as well as the recommendations for future research are also presented. The recommendations are based on the findings stated in Chapter 4.

6.2 RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHOD

The use of qualitative descriptive research method in exploring the phenomenon of sexual risk behaviour among adolescent boys was precisely to collect the experiences, perceptions and knowledge of boys on the subject of risky sexual behaviours. The approach was relevant to soliciting such information from the purposed target group which ultimately led to the findings that are alluded in Chapter 4.

6.3 SUMMARY AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

The contributing factors to risk sexual behaviours embrace negative peer pressure, (individual inability to exercise self-control and choice) alcohol and substance abuse,

lack of knowledge or uninformed sexual intercourse experimentation and domestic violence. The risky sexual behaviours include the non-use of condom during sexual intercourse which may lead to contracting sexually transmitted infection, as well as the multiple sex partners which is mainly signified to be fun for the young boys. Adolescence is a developmental stage with a lot of pressure from family, friends and the internal physical challenges that collectively influence how adolescents revolve around this stage. Therefore, it is significant to consider programmatic approaches that can assist male adolescents' right from family setting to the bigger community within which adolescents develop.

6.4 CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study clearly point to the importance of strengthening sexual reproductive health education of male adolescents particularly at home and in school. Peer education has been identified as the most dominant mode of sex education among boys. Therefore, it is important to encompass the existing social network of adolescents in addressing the subject of sexual reproductive health. This social network takes into account the necessity and importance of family into guiding the path of growth and maturity in matters of sexual reproductive health. Adolescent boys just like their fellow girls need to be guided on this subject.

Peers, school community, media houses, and the church are important and also influence the decisions that adolescent boys take.

The study findings also reveal that the abuse of substance by adolescents contribute to their engagement into risky sexual behaviours. The misconceptions about condom use bear weight on some adolescents hence most of them reported to have firstly-time indulged in a sexual intercourse without the use of condom under the pretext that condoms hamper enjoyment and disturb erection.

6.5 RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations for this study emanate from the study findings. The recommendations are for families, communities, and programming.

These recommendations are expounded as follows:

6.5.1 Families/parents and caregiver roles

- Sexual reproductive health education on the earlier mentioned risk behaviours, including negative peer pressure, should be addressed at home. Parents and guardians need to break away from the culture of silence on the subject and be open and tolerant enough to educate the boy child.
- Familial relations are key in addressing the subject under discussion, boys view the whole subject as an issue of secrecy and therefore reaching out to discuss such topics necessitate rapport building or pre-existing relationship where the boy child can openly and freely share their views, experiences and challenges. Henceforth, it is pivotal for families to embrace the reality of risk behaviours and provide proper guidance without judging or condemning boys.
- There is need for parents' education on how they can effectively support sexual reproductive health education. This will assist in curbing the cultural beliefs of not discussing such topics with young people.

6.5.2 National programming

- The study recognises the need for government to increase programmes and activities geared towards public education on boy's sexual reproductive health, ways of providing guidance both in schools and at home.
- Reinforcing youth friendly agencies and empowering peer education initiatives as touch points for reaching out to boys.
- There is need for collaborative efforts on behaviour modification at schools, churches, community based organisations, and social teen clubs.

6.5.3 Community Interventions

- Addressing risk behaviours with boys requires existence of relationship between adults and boys. It is essential for communities to have peer sexual reproductive

health educators and models who are strategically positioned in activities that attract boys.

- Reflective and testimonial education is needed from men with comparable childhood experiences for purposes of mentoring and coaching.

6.6 CONTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY

This study report will be submitted to SOS Children's Villages of Botswana as an information document that will provide input to the organizational programmatic planning. The study report will further guide their organisational programme development particularly in creating a culture of incorporating adolescent boys in sex related discussions in the home environment. Moreover, the study findings may be considered for experience sharing with other likeminded organisation in Botswana for purposes of improving the support system towards the adolescent boys.

6.7 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The limitations of this study include:

- Generalisation of the study findings must be done with caution bearing that the sample size was small and that the study focused only on adolescent boys aged 13-20 from an institutional home.
- Key factors such as views of carers or family adults were not explored directly with the adults since the study was premised on getting to understand factors to sexual risk behaviours from the perspective of adolescent boys themselves.
- Factors influencing risk sexual behaviours are complex and therefore there is no single leading cause of risk behaviours.
- Invoking sexual experiences is a private subject which at some point during the data collection led to a few participants being shy of discussing the subject although they came on board after the researcher's thorough probing.

6.8 CONCLUSION

Alcohol and substance use, presence of peer pressure, lack of knowledge and domestic violence contribute to boys' sexual risk behaviours. Consequently, youth friendly services on sexual reproductive health should be provided at schools, community level as well as capacitating family members to positively model and support responsive youth programmes specifically for the adolescent boy. The concept of sex education and guidance at all levels of adolescent sexual health and support in the country needs reinforcement.

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ANNEXURES

ANNEXURE A: UNISA ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

**UNIVERSITY OF SOUTH AFRICA
Health Studies Higher Degrees Committee
College of Human Sciences
ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE**

REC-012714-039

HS HDC/440/2015

Date: 4 November 2015 Student No: 4636-514-1

Project Title: Psychosocial factors contributing to sexual risk behaviours among adolescent boys in Botswana.

Researcher: Reginah Pearl Malebogo Mmisi-Nfila

Degree: Masters in Public Health Code: DIS4986

Supervisor: Prof GB Thupayagale-Tshweneagae

Qualification: D Tech

Joint Supervisor: Dr S Sibanda

DECISION OF COMMITTEE

Approved

Conditionally Approved

ANNEXURE B: PERMISSION TO CONDUCT THE STUDY IN SOS CHILDREN'S VILLAGES

SOS Children's Village Association of Botswana

National Office
P O Box 30396
Tlokweng
Plot 584 Losunyaneng Ward
Gaborone, Botswana
Tel / Fax: +267 3953220
soscvc@info.bw

1 December 2015

Reginah Pearl Malebogo Mmisi-Nfila

Serowe

Reginah

Permission to conduct study in SOS Children's Villages

We refer to your request to conduct 'Psychosocial factors contributing to sexual risk behaviors among adolescent boys in Botswana' project.

Permission is hereby granted for you to conduct such a study, within the SOS Children's Village programs on condition that you take into account the best interest of a child in line with the SOSCV Child Protection Policy and the Children's Act of Botswana.

Should you require any further information please do not hesitate to contact the undersigned.

Yours faithfully

SOS Children's Village

Tirafalo Rabasimane

HR Manager

A loving home for every child

ANNEXURE C: INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR INDIVIDUAL INTERVIEWS AND FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE SEXUAL RISK BEHAVIOURS AMONG ADOLESCENT BOYS IN BOTSWANA

1. What is your understanding of sexual risk behaviour? And what do you think makes adolescent boys behave in a risky sexual manner? (Main question)

Probes: Depending on the responses

- What kind of risk sexual behaviours do boys exhibit.
 - Give examples of such behaviours
 - Can you explain your understanding of the risk sexual behaviours more...
2. What do you think is the reason for adolescent boys involvement in the mentioned sexual behaviours

Probes:

- Do they like what they do? If yes/ no why
- Do they face any challenges

3. How do you perceive sexual risk behaviour

Probes:

- Do you recognize sexual risk behaviour like your peers
- What makes boys perceive sexual risk the way they do

4. What could be done to change the boys perceptions about risk behaviours

Probes:

- What should be improved
- Who and how can these behaviours be challenged

ANNEXURE D: INFORMED CONSENT

INFORMED CONSENT

I hereby confirm that the researcher has informed me about the nature, conduct, benefits and risks of the study. I have also received, read and understood the written information (participant information leaflet and informed consent) regarding the study.

I am aware that the results of the study, including personal details regarding my age, marital status, nationality, cultural group, employment status and duration, monthly income, educational level and HIV status will be anonymously processed into a research report.

I am aware that my participation in this study is entirely voluntary and I may refuse or at any stage, withdraw my consent and participation in the study without any reason. I had sufficient opportunity to ask questions and of my own free will declare myself prepared to participate in the study.

Participant’s name _____ (Please print)

Participant’s signature _____ Date _____

Researcher’s name _____ (Please print)

Researcher’s signature _____ Date _____

I, ----- (researcher) herewith confirm that the above

participant has been informed fully about the nature, conduct and risks of the above study.

Witness’s name _____ (Please print)

Witness’s signature _____ Date _____

VERBAL PATIENT INFORMED CONSENT (applicable when participants cannot read or write)

I, the undersigned, _____ (researcher) have read and have fully explained to the participant named _____, the information leaflet, which has indicated the nature and purpose of the study in which I have asked the participant to participate in this study. I have explained both the possible risks and benefits of the study. The participant indicated that s/he understands that s/he will be free to withdraw from the study at any time for any reason and without jeopardising his/her employment status.

I hereby certify that the participant has agreed to participate in this study.

Participant's name _____ (Please print)

Researcher's name _____ (Please print)

Researcher's signature _____ Date _____

Please note: The implication of being interviewed and recorded during the interview is that informed consent has been obtained from you. Thus, any information derived from your interview may be used for publication by the investigator. As all data is anonymous, you must understand that you will not be able to recall your consent, as information will not be traceable.

